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Master Thesis

**Modelling LAI of Alpine Grassland from Sentinel-1
SAR and Sentinel-2 Data using Spatial Gap-filling
in North-Eastern Italy**

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ABSTRACT

Alpine grasslands are crucial ecosystem providers and one of the most threatened terrestrial habitats in the EU. Extreme heat and drought events become more frequent with climate change and lead to yield losses, making continuous, large-scale monitoring of grassland essential. Remote sensing derived Leaf Area Index (LAI) is a key biophysical parameter for grassland yield. However, LAI from optical sensors like Sentinel-2 (S2) is affected by clouds which cause gaps in the time series. Cloud-free LAI can be obtained by data fusion with cloud-penetrating Sentinel-1 (S1) SAR data. This thesis investigates the potential of S1 together with auxiliary predictors (day of the year, precipitation, temperature, and altitudinal class) in a data fusion approach for the spatial gap-filling of LAI from S2. Different machine learning algorithms, including the Gaussian Process Regressor (GPR), Random Forest Regressor (RF), CatBoost, and the multiple-variable Linear Regressor (LR) as benchmark, are trained and validated over Alpine grasslands in North-Eastern Italy for the years 2020-2022. They are tested against in-situ and S2 LAI measurements over eight parcels and unseen test meadows in 2023. In the validation, RF performs best ($R^2=0.70$, $RMSE=0.97$), though the test reveals that the models are not robust and perform poorly. Here, CatBoost is the best-suited model in achieving $R^2=0.16$ and $RMSE=1.34$ against S2 LAI. The GPR performs second-best ($R^2=0.11$, $RMSE=1.37$), surpassing the RF and LR. The test against the in-situ LAI states strong underestimations with high RMSE for all models. All models rely on auxiliary predictors which discloses that S1 is difficult to interpret. The low performance is accounted to the models relying too strongly on these features as the management activities cannot be identified properly. In conclusion, S1, especially using CatBoost or GPR, has a large potential to accurately fill the cloud-related gaps in S2 LAI over Alpine grasslands. In the future, the models should be based more on S1, for example using polarimetric decomposition of the SAR signal to enhance its interpretability without auxiliary predictors. Alternative models like the Multioutput Gaussian Process together with active learning should be investigated, especially with only one active S1 sensor in orbit.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Grassland ecosystems cover about a third of the Earth's landmass (Latham et al., 2014). They are dominated by grass species, herbs, and shrubs and are characterised by the regular removal of biomass through grazing, mowing, fire, drought, or cutting of shrubs (Hobohm et al., 2021; White et al., 2000). Natural grasslands and rangelands like steppes and savannas are managed by grazing. Human-generated or -improved grasslands like Alpine grasslands instead are intensively managed for more production by fertilisation, grazing, mowing, and reseeded (Ali et al., 2016). Alpine grasslands are crucial ecosystem service providers and play a central role in providing forage for livestock and serving as a place for recreation in tourism (Bernués et al., 2014; Thom et al., 2022). Other important services consist of preventing soil erosion, purifying water, and regulating the climate through carbon sequestration. Grasslands maintain biodiversity, support the nutrient cycles, and are of aesthetic and cultural significance (Bernués et al., 2014; Gibon, 2005; Hobohm et al., 2021; White et al., 2000).

Grasslands are one of the most threatened terrestrial habitats in the EU and the major threats are agricultural intensification and rural abandonment (European Commission. Directorate General for the Environment, 2016). Especially the Alpine and sub-alpine grasslands are potentially strongly impacted by climate change (ibid.). With climate change, the Alps will face a drier and warmer climate (IPCC, 2023; Kotlarski et al., 2023), and extreme heat and drought events become more frequent (Spinoni et al., 2018). The impacts of climate change range from temporarily reduced productivity and yield losses up to long-term changes in ecosystems (Crausbay et al., 2017; IPCC, 2023) and reducing the grasslands' ability to mitigate climate change by carbon sequestration and evapotranspiration (Cox et al., 2000; Teuling et al., 2010). Milder and shorter winters and changes in precipitation will decrease the grassland extent and alter the species composition by being particularly influential for vegetation adapted to shorter growing seasons (Dibari et al., 2020; Möhl et al., 2023).

Timely, large-scale monitoring of grassland production is crucial in times of climate change and yield losses (Reinermann et al., 2020; Shoko et al., 2016). However, monitoring grasslands through in situ observations is expensive and not applicable to large areas (Ali et al., 2016). Remote sensing instead provides cost-effective information across large areas (Kerr and Ostrovsky, 2003). The Leaf Area Index (LAI) is measured in square meters per square meter [m^2m^{-2}] – or is unitless (Zheng and Moskal, 2009) – and was developed by Watson (1947) to compare agricultural yields. Since then it had different definitions but is most commonly defined as half the total intercepting foliage area per unit ground surface area (Chen and Black, 1992; cf. Zheng and Moskal, 2009). The LAI is a key biophysical parameter, being closely related to plant productivity and health as the light interception of vegetation is mostly determined by its LAI (Van Wijk and Williams, 2005). Therefore, LAI is used for multiple

vegetation variables in remote sensing (Wang, 2019) and shows a high correlation with grassland yield (Castelli et al., 2023).

LAI derived from optical remote sensing data like Sentinel-2 (S2) is often affected by the frequent cloud coverage in central Europe, which causes spatial and temporal gaps in the time series and renders grassland monitoring more challenging (Castelli et al., 2023; Reinermann et al., 2022). Cloud-free LAI products, obtained by data fusion or gap-filling strategies, are spatially (and temporally) more continuous and accurate (Kooistra et al., 2024), and even mandatory for meaningful results (Pipia et al., 2021).

Gap-filling is usually done using auxiliary data from the same sensor (Shu et al., 2022). Filling strategies are classified into spatial-, temporal-, spectral-based, and hybrid methods, depending on the source of auxiliary information (Shen et al., 2015; Shu et al., 2022). They are commonly done using interpolation techniques, linear regression, or machine learning algorithms (Salinero-Delgado et al., 2021; Sun and Xu, 2021). In the latter, non-linear regressor models like the Gaussian Process Regressor (GPR) predict missing pixel values and are widely tested for gap-filling in LAI time series (Belda et al., 2020; Mateo-Sanchis et al., 2018; Pipia et al., 2021). However, the gap-filling techniques on the same sensor are limited, especially with wide and frequent cloud coverage (Shu et al., 2022). Additionally, they cannot accurately account for the rapid changes in managed grasslands. For instance, if a mowing event goes unnoticed due to cloud coverage, gap-filling using the common strategies is not able to account for it (cf. Garioud et al., 2020).

Data fusion, often called a gap-filling strategy, instead combines information from two or more sensors of different resolutions, usually using a sensor with a coarse spatial resolution to enrich a high-resolution time series (Shu et al., 2022). Fusion methods are based on linear unmixing, weighted functions, Bayesian estimation, machine learning models, or hybrid methods (Zhu et al., 2018). Although data fusion with other optical imagery reduces the amount of unavailable data, it does not solve the cloud problem. In contrast, data fusion with cloud-penetrating SAR data shows great potential and is increasingly exploited (Garioud et al., 2020) as this delivers information on the grassland where optical sensors are hampered by clouds. Therefore, especially the fusion with SAR data can be favourable for regions with frequent cloud coverage (Kooistra et al., 2024). Holtgrave et al. (2020) pointed out that the correlation between optical and SAR data might not be high enough to make them interchangeable, thus suggesting them to fill gaps in optical data or identify abrupt changes.

The active C-band SAR sensor Sentinel-1 (S1) can penetrate clouds and, has already proven great potential to fill the (spatial) gaps in the LAI time series of S2 (e.g., Castelli et al., 2023; Holtgrave et al., 2020; Martinez et al., 2021; Mercier et al., 2020; Pipia et al., 2019; Wang,

2019). Additionally, S1 can provide useful additional information about the vegetation structure and moisture by penetrating the grass canopy and its dual polarisation interacting with the geometric and dielectric properties of the vegetation (Chang and Shoshany, 2016; Garioud et al., 2020; Holtgrave et al., 2020). Given that mowing events lead to rapid changes in the LAI, high temporal resolution is needed to monitor managed grassland (Reinermann et al., 2020). Also, high spatial resolution is needed as grassland meadows are relatively small and to sense variations within the meadows (Ali et al., 2016; Reinermann et al., 2020) – particularly in heterogeneous study areas like the Alps (Weiss and Walsh, 2009). The spatial resolution, the acquisition of S1 in both ascending and descending orbits, as well as the constellation from 2016-2021 is advantageous. Unfortunately, the outage of S1-B strongly reduces the monitoring potential with only one satellite in orbit before the launch of S1-C and –D.

Studies on the use of SAR for grassland production and yield estimation are less frequent (cf. Ali et al., 2016; Crabbe et al., 2019; Reinermann et al., 2020) compared to forests above-ground biomass (AGB) and crops (e.g., Chang and Shoshany, 2016; Laurin et al., 2018). Some studies have highlighted the potential of SAR data for grassland (Barrett et al., 2014; Chiarito et al., 2021; Naidoo et al., 2019), and have increasingly combined optical, SAR, and also auxiliary data (Castelli et al., 2023; Holtgrave et al., 2020; Naidoo et al., 2019; Nickmilder et al., 2021; Raab et al., 2020; Wang, 2019). Reinermann et al. (2020) suggested monitoring the production for heterogeneous grasslands across multiple seasons, with a need for information on management and incorporating the heterogeneity in grasslands for future large-scale monitoring of grassland yield.

Thus, this thesis aims to investigate the potential of S1 SAR data and auxiliary predictors in a data fusion approach using machine learning models for spatial gap-filling of LAI from S2 optical data. This is done for Alpine grasslands in North-Eastern Italy over multiple growing seasons. The model training spans the years 2020 to 2022 and is applied to gap-fill 2023 for validation together with field data collected over eight forage production meadows. The main research questions of the thesis are:

- What is the potential of S1 SAR data to fill the gaps resulting from cloud coverage in S2 LAI data?
- Which (auxiliary) features and machine learning approaches are best suited for this aim?
- What is the accuracy of the gap-filled maps?

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The schematic workflow used in this thesis is shown in Figure 1 and contains the different steps explained in the following. The chapter numbers are indicated. The input data (2.2) over the selected meadows of the study area (2.1) is used to create a database for modelling. The best-performing regressor models to estimate the LAI are selected (2.3). Finally, the models are validated (2.4) for unseen meadows in 2023 and against the S2 LAI and ground data sampled in the field campaign.

Figure 1 Workflow to model LAI of Alpine grassland using spatial gap-filling.

2.1 STUDY AREA

The study area is the region Trentino-South Tyrol which covers the Autonomous Provinces of Trento and Bolzano in North-Eastern Italy (~13.600 km²), see Figure 2. Only a small part of the area of interest falls in the province of Trento, most investigated grassland is in the province of Bolzano. The region is in the southern Alps and Dolomites and has a strong topographic variation ranging from 66 m at Lake Garda to Mt. Ortles at 3905 m. The climatic condition results from this topography: Atlantic low-pressure systems are stopped by the main ridge of the Alps and warm Mediterranean air masses reach through the broad Adige Valley. This causes a high number of sunny days and a relatively low annual precipitation. The precipitation results mostly from Mediterranean cyclones in summer and least in winter, varying between

450-500 mm in the dry Venosta Valley and 1800 mm in southern Trentino (Crespi et al., 2021; Pedrotti, 2018). Precipitation and temperature are of high spatial variability, especially along elevation gradients in narrow valleys (Crespi et al., 2021). The majority of agricultural area in both provinces is used as grassland, 70% in the Province of Bolzano and 84% in Trento (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2020a, 2020b).

Figure 2 Location of the study area, its elevation, and the permanent meadows.
Imagery: Google, © 2024 TerraMetrics.

2.1.1 MEADOW CLASSIFICATION ACCORDING TO ALTITUDINAL BELTS

With every increase of 100 m elevation in the Alps the phenological phases begin 3.8 days later (Cornelius et al., 2013) and the growing season lasts 6-7 days shorter (Zerbe, 2023). Also, the temperature differences at high elevations can be very distinct, hot during the day and potentially freezing at nighttime throughout the entire year (ibid.). Vegetation belts represent a zonal series of similar climatic and soil conditions based on altitude, comparable

to vegetation zones that group along latitude (Pedrotti, 2018). Vegetation or so-called altitudinal belts thus resemble climate classifications (Rubel et al., 2017). On south-facing, sunny slopes altitudinal belts occur relatively higher than on north-facing, shady slopes and similarly higher on leeward than on windward slopes (Zhang and Zhao, 2020). Local patterns result in variations of altitudinal belts (ibid.) but in general, the belts for Trentino-South Tyrol can be defined as: colline (< 800 m), submontane 800-1,200 m, montane 1,200-1,850 m, subalpine 1,850-2,300 m, alpine 2,300-2,800 m, subnival 2,800-3,100 m, and nival > 3,100 m (Erschbamer et al., 2010; Leuschner and Ellenberg, 2017; Rubel et al., 2017; Pedrotti, 2018).

The meadows in the study area lay between 230.5 and 2437.5 m ASL. They are first classified into north- and south-facing meadows based on their mean north-ness (cosine of the aspect). As the classes should have similar sizes, e.g., to avoid overfitting of small classes, both north- and south-facing meadows are classified into the altitudinal belts based on the quantiles of mean elevation. This results in the 8 classes indicated in Figure 3, with borders being lower for north-facing slopes.

Figure 3 Classification-scheme of the meadows according to altitudinal belts with respective borders for north and south-facing meadows.

The altitudinal class is examined as an input feature in the modelling process and is used to provide stratified selections over all meadows (2.1.2). This way meadows that have similar climatic and thus presumably similar grass growth conditions are classified together. At the same time, this classification is done without any verification against LAI to avoid inducing too strict presumptions in the modelling process.

2.1.2 SELECTION OF THE MEADOWS

To ensure that the model applies to the whole area of interest the features have to be similar to the features the model was trained with (Meyer and Pebesma, 2021). At the same time, including all meadows of the provinces is not feasible, thus representative meadows must be selected.

The Autonomous Province Bozen (2022) maintains an information system for agriculture and forestry called LAFIS where all data concerning these areas is stored. The respective LAFIS shapefile contains polygons of single parcels of various grassland types and is used to select the representative meadows. Only the major grassland type of permanent meadows is used for modelling, this is 81,181 of the 102,159 meadows. Other types like “Meadow of special area/Lean meadows and fen meadows” or “Meadow of special area/Species-rich Mountain meadows” could induce variation which would make modelling based on multiple years difficult or require dedicated treatment. The fact that also the land cover of permanent meadows can change over time should be considered though is not part of this study.

As the borders are often close to other land use classes such as forests or roads, a buffer ensures that no mixed signal from either border pixels of the remote sensing data or imprecisely mapped meadows affects the model performance. Thus, the meadow polygons are buffered by one diagonal 10 m pixel (-14.15 m) to make sure all pixels are completely within the meadow. At the same time, this means that only the inner pixels can be predicted from the models and future yield estimations for whole meadows must be upscaled for the missing pixels by the parcel area.

The smallest field site for the validation has about 0.4 ha when buffered (see 2.2.6). Meadows with an area smaller than this are filtered out, still guaranteeing the model to be able to model all field sites. This way, very tiny meadows are removed from the database. The meadows where field data is collected are also excluded from the database for independent validation (cf. 2.4.5). This results in 34,318 meadows left. As 3 years of data (2020-2022) over this many meadows with multiple pixels would result in a database too big to be used for modelling, just 10% (3431) of these meadows are selected. To take a representative sample, the selection is based on the classification according to the altitudinal belts introduced in 2.1.1.

2.2 DATA

The dataset used to model the LAI over selected meadows in the study area consists of the target variable S2 LAI (2.2.1), and S1 SAR data (2.2.2), along with meteorological data (2.2.3) (see Figure 4), the day of the year (2.2.4), and the altitudinal class (2.1.1) which are examined as auxiliary input features. Ground measurements (2.2.6) and an independent test-set (2.2.8) are used for validation.

S2 14.08.2023

S1 SAR 15.08.2023

Meteorological data 14.08.2023

Figure 4 Data used for modelling. Exemplarily for the 14.08.2023.

2.2.1 SENTINEL-2 LAI

The Copernicus S2 mission consists of two polar-orbiting satellites launched in 2015 (S2-A) and 2017 (S2-B). Their MultiSpectral Instrument (MSI) is a push-broom sensor with 290 km swath width and 13 spectral bands ranging from the visible to near and short wave infra-red and 10 to 60 m spatial resolution (Drusch et al., 2012). Thanks to the constellation, the revisit time is 2-3 days at mid-latitudes like the Alps.

The LAI is derived from S2 L2A optical data for the years 2020 to 2023 over five tiles that are needed to cover the whole study area (T32TPR, -TPS, -TPT, -TQS, and -TQT). The S2 L2A is atmospherically corrected from top-of-atmosphere (TOA) S2 L1C scenes to bottom-of-atmosphere (BOA)/surface reflectance using the Sen2Cor processor (European Space Agency, n.d.). This preprocessing was done by Eurac Research for the scenes until 31.07.2023 and since then the L2A data has been downloaded from the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (Copernicus, n.d.). It is important to note that different versions of Sen2Cor have been used over the years and especially the switch to the Copernicus L2A product could lead to differences from August 2023 onwards.

The LAI is generated using the SNAP Biophysical Processor (Weiss et al., 2020) by the S2ToolBox version 9.0.2 (SNAP version 9.0.6). To automate the calculation, a processing graph is applied in the terminal looping over the S2 files. The biophysical processor offers neural network algorithms for biophysical parameters in 10 m and 20 m resolution, thus with the resolution of the different S2 bands taking different bands for the calculation. For heterogeneous areas, Weiss et al. (2020) recommend not to resample and use the 10 m algorithm based on the three 10 m bands (B3, B4, B8). Thus, here the data is resampled to 10 m using the nearest neighbour and fed into the 20 m neural network instead which considers eight bands (B3, B4, B5, B6, B7, B8, B8a, B11, B12). This has been suggested for grassland LAI for the same study area by Castelli et al. (2023), includes more spectral information, and is overall more accurate (Weiss et al., 2020).

Afterward, the LAI files are masked to remove pixels affected by clouds, cloud shadows, snow, and water. This is done using the Fmask algorithm (Frantz et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2015; Zhu and Woodcock, 2012) implemented in the python-fmask. The authors suggest using a spatial resolution of 20 m as a higher resolution is not expected to be more accurate (Neil Flood and Sam Gillingham, 2015). The masks are derived from S2 L1C data and are applied to the S2 LAI where only pixels classified as "clear" (1) are kept excluding any pixels affected by the above-mentioned coverages. The range of LAI is 0-8 according to Weiss et al. (2020) thus values outside these thresholds are masked. The quality band delivered by the biophysical processor however is not used for masking. It indicates where the input or output data is out

of range. This is already covered by the cloud and threshold masking and as the data is just used for known land cover (grassland), it is assumed that the land cover is suited for LAI calculations. In contrast, masking with the quality band could result in losing data where, e.g., a meadow has been recently mowed and appears like a non-vegetated area that seems not adequate for the LAI calculation.

It must be remarked that the Simplified Level 2 Prototype Processor (SL2P) which is implemented in the SNAP biophysical processor for the calculation of the biophysical parameters shows imprecisions: Two mistakes in the SL2P which propagated to the SNAP biophysical processor influence both the product and the quality flags. In the product calculation, the parameters for the regression calibration were wrongly set when the parameters were out of range. In the quality flags, too many output values were flagged as out of range (Fernandes et al., 2023). The performance of the LAI estimations over spatially homogenous canopies like grasslands is good whilst it underestimates in-situ LAI over the heterogeneous canopies of forests (Brown et al., 2021). The imprecisions in the quality flag instead are another reason not to use it for masking.

2.2.2 SENTINEL-1 SAR DATA

The Copernicus S1 mission is like the S2 a constellation of two satellites. They were launched in 2014 and 2016, though S1-B's mission ended in December 2021 due to anomalies in the instrument's power supply (European Space Agency, 2022). The satellites carry a C-band SAR antenna in dual polarisation (HH + HV or VV + VH). Due to the constellation and the acquisition during day and night in ascending and descending orbits the temporal resolution is dense until 2021. Four imaging modes with different resolutions and coverage are available, for example, the Interferometric Wide-swath mode (IW) allows the combination of a large swath width (> 250 m) with a high spatial resolution (5 x 20 m). The product levels available from Copernicus are Level-1 and consist of Slant Range, Single-Look Complex (SLC) and the Ground Range, Multi-Look, Detected (GRD) products (Torres et al., 2012). Further pre-processing is left to the user.

2.2.2.1 Radiometrically Terrain Corrected (RTC)

Mountainous terrain and the side-looking radar geometry cause radiometric and geometric distortions in the SAR backscatter. Radiometrically, slopes facing the sensor appear brighter than those facing away. This happens because the backscatter intensity depends on the local incidence angle, meaning that if the angle is smaller more radiation is scattered back to the sensor (Kaplan et al., 2021; Meyer, 2019). Geometrically, the slopes facing the antenna look foreshortened or compressed (Meyer, 2019), while slopes looking away seem elongated. Where the slopes are very steep and the incidence angle small, layover occurs so that the

signal from the summit reaches the sensor before the one of the mountain foot. Radar shadow occurs where due to the side-looking angle of the sensor no signal reaches the slopes facing away from the sensor (ibid.). Especially narrow valleys and steep mountain ridges in the range direction of the sensor (north-south facing) are affected by radar shadow as this topography does not allow any signal to reach these areas either in ascending or descending orbit, thus resulting in no data available here.

The radiometric and geometric distortions make change detection or time series analysis of SAR data from different sensors, in different orbits or viewing angles difficult or incomparable (Kaplan et al., 2021; Meyer, 2019; Small, 2011). Only data from the same orbit and with similar local incidence angles could be used for the analysis which reduces the temporal resolution drastically (Kaplan et al., 2021). Hence, the radiometric and geometric correction is needed and even called crucial to derive biophysical parameters (Loew and Mauser, 2007). The comparison between GRD and different RTC products by Flores-Anderson et al. (2023) even implies not using the GRD without any radiometric and geometric correction due to its inferior performance and suggests using RTC instead. For this reason, the S1 level I use here is the RTC.

The radiometric terrain correction or radiometric terrain flattening removes the systematic terrain-induced effects and normalizes the backscatter for the local illuminated area regarding the topography (Small, 2011). Different techniques have been proposed and usually, the method by Small (2011) is favoured despite being computationally demanding and requiring a high-resolution DEM (Shiroma et al., 2022). The DEM is used in the radiometric image simulation to determine the local illuminated area by the sensor. The local illuminated area is estimated by first deriving the elevation of the four corners of every pixel from the DEM, then dividing them into triangular planes and reprojecting them to the plane perpendicular to the radar line of sight. Then the radar brightness (beta-nought backscatter β°) is normalized by dividing it by the local illuminated area to obtain the radiometric terrain-corrected gamma-nought backscatter (γ°) (Small, 2011). Other methods that use ellipsoid-based incident angles and no DEM or normalise from sigma nought (σ°) instead perform less in accounting for the topographic distortions (ibid.). Afterward, the SAR data is geometrically terrain corrected or orthorectified using a DEM to correct the location of the pixels and geometrically project to a flat surface (Meyer, 2019). Additionally, areas with radar shadow or foreshortening can be masked out (Small, 2011).

The S1 RTC data used here is processed by Catalyst and downloaded in 10 m resolution and ascending and descending orbit from the Microsoft Planetary Computer (Microsoft Open Source et al., 2022): The relative orbit numbers covering the study area are 95 and 168 in the descending and 15, 44 and 117 in the ascending track. The data is derived from the S1 GRD

σ° backscatter in the Interferometric Wide Swath (IW) mode. It was first radiometrically calibrated to γ° using the metadata and then radiometrically terrain corrected using a PlanetDEM according to the method of Small, 2011. Pixels affected by radar shadow are flagged and the data is orthorectified (Microsoft Open Source et al., 2022). The fact that this RTC data is not derived from β° backscatter but σ° could be an obstacle as using β° already includes other preprocessing steps.

The ascending and descending orbit are used as separate features. Technically, they could be merged which would increase temporal resolution, especially in times of just one working S1 sensor. This was for example done by Pipia et al. (2019) for a similar approach but a topographically more simple study area in Castile and Leon, Spain. Thus, this approach is left for future investigations.

2.2.2.2 Further Preprocessing

Individual scatterers in one resolution cell contribute to the backscatter signal. As they vary randomly, also neighbouring pixels in homogenous areas, e.g., a meadow, vary randomly in amplitude and phase of the backscatter signal (Meyer, 2019). This speckle is therefore inherent in SAR data, resulting in a signal that resembles noise (Greifeneder et al., 2021) and leads to a higher uncertainty in LAI estimation (Caballero et al., 2022). It can be treated using speckle filtering. Preliminary tests showed that filtering the data increases the correlation of S1 backscatter intensity with S2 LAI. Thus, the S1 RTC is speckle-filtered using the Lee Sigma filter with a 7x7 pixel window (Lee et al., 2009) in Python (version 3.8.16). Then VH and VV are converted from linear, dimensionless γ° backscatter intensity coefficients to dB by logarithmic scaling according to (1). It must be noted that the speckle filtering after the geometric terrain correction could present issues as the latter already alters the properties of the data by resampling and reprojecting.

$$\gamma^\circ[dB] = 10 * \log_{10}(\gamma^\circ) \quad (1)$$

2.2.2.3 Index Calculation

VV and VH backscatter have been successfully used to model grassland biomass with VH usually performing better (Castelli et al., 2023; Crabbe et al., 2019; Wang, 2019). Cross-polarised backscattering as VH is dominated by the volume scattering from within vegetation or from multiple scattering on rough surfaces (McNairn and Brisco, 2004). The VV backscatter instead is characterised by the contribution from the ground and is thus more sensitive to soil moisture (Veloso et al., 2017).

In addition to the VH and VV, also the ratio between VV and VH as well as the radar vegetation index (RVI) are used here. The RVI was developed by Kim and Van Zyl (2009) to segment vegetated surfaces in the SAR data as it is sensitive to the biomass and the vegetation water content by including the above-mentioned polarised bands (Kim and Van Zyl, 2009; Nasirzadehdizaji et al., 2019). The RVI is especially recommended for agricultural vegetation monitoring (Holtgrave et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2013). It has been adapted for dual-polarised data by Trudel (2012) and for use with S1 by Nasirzadehdizaji et al. (2019). Like the NDVI for optical imagery, the RVI values range from 0 to 1, except for double-bounce scattering events that can have values higher than one. Higher values represent more biomass and values close to zero represent smooth bare surface (Kim and Van Zyl, 2009; Kumar et al., 2013). To keep the range between 0 and 1, the RVI and the ratio are calculated using the VV and VH bands in the dimensionless backscatter intensity in a linear scale.

The sum and the difference of VV and VH polarisation developed by Laurin et al. (2018) have been reported as well-performing for forest and maize AGB estimation (Laurin et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2022) and will be tested here as well. Xu et al. (2022) developed SAR polarisation indices for the estimation of maize biomass which could perform advantageous for grassland LAI. All the features derived from the S1 SAR backscatter intensity are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Features derived from S1 SAR backscatter.
VH and VV in dB, except for the ratio and RVI calculation.

Band/Feature	Formula	Reference
VV	–	
VH	–	
ratio	$\frac{VH}{VV}$	
RVI	$\frac{4 * VH}{VV + VH}$	Kim and Van Zyl (2009) Trudel (2012) Nasirzadehdizaji et al. (2019)
Simple additive index (sum)	$VV + VH$	Laurin et al. (2018)
Simple difference index (difference)	$VV - VH$	
Multiplication index (product)	$VV * VH$	Xu et al. (2022)
Ratio index (VH/product)	$\frac{VH}{VV * VH}$	
Ratio index (sum/product)	$\frac{VV + VH}{VV * VH}$	
Square difference index	$VV^2 - VH^2$	

2.2.3 METEOROLOGICAL DATA

In addition to the S1 features also meteorological data is assessed as input features in the gap-filling approach of S2 LAI. This is done to account for the impact of driving climatic variables on grassland productivity (Hobohm et al., 2021) and thus also LAI. The productivity is highly determined by precipitation (Gao et al., 2017), particularly in the early and mid-growing season (cf. Reinermann et al., 2020). The temperature has a negative influence on productivity (Mao et al., 2014) – or positive if in combination with high soil moisture content (Flanagan and Adkinson, 2011). It is the biggest at the beginning of the growing season (cf. Reinermann et al., 2020) as it affects its start (Wang et al., 2020). The relationship between LAI and the precipitation and temperature has often been indicated, e.g., reporting an almost linear relationship between annual average LAI and annual total precipitation up to 1800 mm and similarly for annual mean temperatures from 10-25 °C for different African ecosystems (Li et al., 2019). However, this could behave differently in Alpine grassland ecosystems and also be due to external influences and the climatic variables cannot completely explain the grassland productivity or LAI (Fang et al., 2019; Neuwirth and Hofer, 2013).

The meteorological data used in the gap-filling approach, namely daily total precipitation and daily mean temperature, is developed and provided by Crespi et al. (2021). The dataset is generated using observations from meteorological stations and has a spatial resolution of 250 by 250 m which makes it easy to use. It covers the region of Trentino-South Tyrol since 1980 (Crespi et al., 2021). The daily precipitation is the accumulated precipitation from 8:00 am of the previous day to 8:00 of the date in mm. The daily mean temperature is the average between the maximum and minimum temperature of that day (ibid.). The spatial resolution of 250 m does not match the 10 m which is used for the Sentinel data. This is neglected as precipitation and temperature are considered homogeneous for this spatial unit and whole meadows. Nevertheless, pixels with different LAI and S1 values could have the same precipitation and mean temperature which could induce errors, especially if they have more importance in the prediction than the S1 data. The meteorological data does just account for the climatic circumstances and not for the conditions on the meadows as they are derived from meteorological stations. Thus, changes in vegetation can just be guessed by learned coincidences, and management processes like mowing events are not detectable. This is why it should serve as auxiliary data only and be examined in the feature selection process.

Figure 5 shows the meteorological diagram for all selected meadows based on Crespi et al. (2021). It shows that the temperature in 2023 is comparable to the three previous years until July and slightly higher for August and early autumn. 2023 had the same annual mean temperature of 8.3 °C as the year before though it was warmer than 2020 and 2021. The total precipitation instead was 1091 mm which is much more than the two previous and drier years

and is comparable to 2020. The monthly pattern for 2023 shows that May, July, and October experienced much precipitation with still high temperatures. This way, 2023 can be classified as both hot and rich in precipitation for the selected meadows.

Figure 5 Meteorological diagram for the selected meadows in 2020-2023. Based on the gridded meteorological data by Crespi et al. (2021).

Auxiliary surface soil moisture content (SMC) data, e.g., produced by Eurac Research by using the machine learning algorithm developed by Greifeneder et al. (2021), is not used even though Castelli et al. (2023) found it very useful to estimate LAI from S1. This data with 10 m spatial resolution is based on Landsat-8 optical and thermal bands, S1 SAR, Copernicus Global Land Cover Layer (CGLS-LC100), MOD13Q1 Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), and OpenLandMap (OLM) Soil Information (Greifeneder et al., 2021). It is masked using the CGLS-LC100 in 100 m resolution to include only low vegetated areas (shrubs, herbaceous vegetation, cropland, bare/sparse vegetation, open forest) and thus limited to these areas only (ibid.). This means that due to the low spatial resolution of the land cover mask also grassland close to forest, e.g., can be masked and no SMC data is available here. For this reason, it is not included in this study.

2.2.4 DAY OF THE YEAR

Castelli et al. (2023) used the day of the year (DOY) as an input feature in modelling S2 LAI, together with S1 features and soil moisture content over grassland in the northwest of South Tyrol for 2017. As the DOY along with the VH and soil moisture content yielded the best performance in their GPR model (ibid.), the input feature is assessed also in this study. However, caution is advised as it could generalise potential seasonal differences over the whole area of interest and could lead to an over-importance of the seasonality in predicting LAI.

2.2.5 DIGITAL ELEVATION MODEL

A digital elevation model (DEM) is needed for the classification into altitudinal belts. The EU DEM version 1.1 has a high spatial resolution of 25 m and was downloaded from the European Environment Agency (2016). It is resampled to the 10 m resolution of the S2 LAI and slope and aspect are calculated using GDAL 3.4.1 within QGIS 3.22.4. It has to be noted that the EU DEM is not continued any further by the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service and since 2019 the Copernicus Global DEM in 30 m (GLO-30) has been recommended instead (European Environment Agency, 2024). Here the EU DEM is still used because of the slightly higher resolution.

2.2.6 IN-SITU MEASUREMENTS

The gap-filled LAI is validated against in-situ measurements from eight forage production meadows shown in the map in Figure 6 and specified in Appendix A: The two sites in Fondo (F) lay in the Province of Trento, whereas the sites of Laurein (L) and Ritten (R) are in the Province of Bolzano. Six of eight meadows are south-facing (S) so that R1, R3, and R5 fall in the “S Submontane”, L2 in the “S Lower montane” and F1 and F2 in the “S Colline” class. R4 and L1 are north-facing (N) and both in the “N Lower montane” class. With 0.37 ha L2 is the smallest site, and F1 is the biggest site with 1.38 ha.

The sampling is bi-weekly from April to the end of October 2023, rotating the sites of Ritten with Fondo and Laurein. At each sampling, three single measurements are made within the respective site, located in the centre of an S2 pixel and placed to represent the whole pixel. A wooden frame of 0.25 m² is used for measuring. The LAI is measured with the LI-COR LAI-2200C Plant Canopy Analyzer, using the 180° view cap to exclude the operator from the sensor’s view for one reading above (A) and five readings below (B) the grass canopy. The ratio between the A and averaged B readings is used to calculate the transmittance and subsequently the foliage amount (LAI) of the canopy. To prevent scattering due to direct sunlight, the sensor must be shaded during all measurements (LI-COR, 2023). The LAI

measurement is replicated three more times in the vicinity of the wooden quadrat to avoid outliers and represent the whole pixel (Figure 7a).

Figure 6 Location and specifications of the field sites.

The Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) is determined using the Apogee Instruments MQ-301X Line Quantum. Afterward, the soil moisture content (HydroSense II Water Content Sensor CS658), vegetation composition (graminoids, leguminoids, other plants), and chlorophyll content (Konica Minolta Chlorophyll Meter SPAD-502Plus) are measured. Also, the weather condition is recorded, the swart height is measured using a meter stick and a rising plate meter and lodging is noted. Lodged vegetation, schematically depicted in Figure 7b, is leaning towards the ground or even lying flat, typically when the vegetation is very tall or tilts after heavy precipitation (Reddersen et al., 2014). The changed geometry of the grass alters the estimation of LAI and results in an underestimation of yield (Castelli et al., 2023).

Management processes like mowing, grazing by livestock, and fertilization are registered for the analysis of the field measurements. Lastly, the yield is obtained from destructive samples cut 5 cm above the ground within the wood frame and then dried in an oven at 60°C and 0%

relative humidity. Similar measurements have been collected by Laimburg Research Centre (Castelli et al., 2023) for the growing seasons of 2021-2022.

Figure 7 a) Exemplary ground measurement sampling on one day on L1 with replicate measurements of LAI. b) Stages of lodging.

2.2.7 DATASET

The dataset for the model selection is created using 80% of the selected meadows and spans the years 2020-2022. The data extraction is done in R (version 4.3.2). If duplicated acquisitions per day are present, for example, due to constellations, the mean is taken. Then in Python, the datasets of LAI, S1, and meteorological data are combined into one by their date and coordinates. The maximum time difference between matching observations is one day, preferring the nearest observation in time but the exact coordinates. Then the DOY is calculated from the date. The resulting database contains the values of LAI, S1 RTC features, precipitation, temperature, DOY, and the class for every pixel per date for the selected meadows. The values are rounded to three decimal places.

In total, the dataset from 2020-2022 contains ten million observations. To reduce the computation time 10% of the samples are selected in a stratified manner according to the altitudinal classification to ensure that observations of every class are used in the training and validation. The remaining 90% are used for validation. This is still many observations, for comparison, Greifeneder et al. (2021) used 80% of 30,000 observations for model training. Because GPR is very time-consuming when training with many samples and performs very well on a small database (2.3.1.2), the training set for GPR is further reduced to 5,000 randomly selected samples, a reasonable limit according to Verrelst et al. (2016).

Another possibility would be to use Active Learning (AL) to reduce the size of a training database by selecting the most useful samples and increasing the accuracy in estimating biophysical parameters at the same time (Verrelst et al., 2016). Also, Berger et al. (2021) reported that models that were trained with AL-optimized training sets yielded better results than the ones trained with randomly sampled sets. Due to the implementation of the models in pipelines (2.3.2), the AL is difficult to implement and would increase the computation time. Thus, even if the accuracies are potentially lower, the samples are selected randomly but stratified.

2.2.8 TEST-SET

For easier differentiation between the validation set used in model training for the years 2020-2022, the set for the year 2023 is called the “test-set” in this study. It is created similarly to the dataset but covers the 20% selected meadows that have not been used in model training and allows LAI to bear gaps (NA). This way the test-set is independent both in time and location, without introducing an overestimation of the accuracy due to the autocorrelation of observations close in time and space (Meyer et al., 2018).

2.3 MACHINE LEARNING FOR DATA FUSION

To examine the suitability of S1 for the estimation of grassland LAI, different sets of input features, consisting of S1 and auxiliary features, are compared. Several machine learning algorithms (2.3.1) introduced in the following are examined to find the best-suited model for data fusion.

2.3.1 NON-LINEAR REGRESSION MODELS

As few relations in nature are linear, also remote sensing-based biophysical parameters show non-linear behaviour (Schulz et al., 2018). Especially the SAR signal is affected by different surface properties which makes it difficult to interpret without additional information (Holtgrave et al., 2020; Pipia et al., 2019). Non-linear regression models can learn complex non-linear relationships and are thus very useful for remote sensing models (Ali et al., 2015; Schulz et al., 2018). The non-linear regressors used here are the Random Forest Regressor (RF), the Gaussian Process Regressor (GPR), and the CatBoost Regressor. A simple multiple-variable Linear Regression model (LR) is trained as well and serves as a benchmark to verify if the more complex and computationally time-consuming non-linear regression is of advantage to estimate grassland LAI.

The models are chosen because they are widely used, state-of-the-art, or outperforming other models: RF is widely used in remote sensing, especially for classification purposes, due to its high accuracy (Belgiu and Drăguț, 2016). GPR is established for the estimation of LAI from SAR data (Castelli et al., 2023; Mercier et al., 2020; Pipia et al., 2019). The CatBoost outperforms other gradient-boosting algorithms based on decision trees like the LightGBM and XGBoost (Prokhorenkova et al., 2017). CatBoost is rarely used in remote sensing, though first studies regarding the prediction of forest AGB from (multi-) satellite data using CatBoost concluded that it outperformed other algorithms like RF and XGBoost (Luo et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2020). In wheat yield prediction from S1 and S2 CatBoost provided the best results as well when compared to RF, a multiple LR, and a Support Vector Machine (Uribeetxebarria et al., 2023).

2.3.1.1 Random Forest Regressor

The Random Forest Regressor (RF) is based on the collective of decision trees in a forest (Breiman, 2001). RF is a bagging method, which means that all trees are built independently using bootstrap (random) samples of the training data, and also the feature selection at each node is random (ibid.). This randomness is used to decrease the variance of the model (Hastie et al., 2009). The final prediction is the average of all trees (Breiman, 2001; Hastie et al., 2009) which is in contrast to boosting methods where the result is based on weight (Hastie et al., 2009; Liaw and Wiener, 2002). In scikit-learn, the result is averaged by the probability given

by single trees (scikit-learn, 2024a). With many trees in a forest, the regressor becomes more precise in predicting and robust to noise and overfitting (Breiman, 2001).

For RF, the number of trees in the forest ($n_{\text{estimators}}$) and the maximum number of input features (max_features) to find the best split at each node has to be set (scikit-learn, 2024a). Here, the max_features are not tuned but set to all input features, as through the feature selection the best-suited features are selected.

2.3.1.2 Gaussian Process Regressor

The Gaussian Process Regressor (GPR) is a nonparametric, kernel-based, probabilistic (Bayesian) machine-learning regression algorithm (Rasmussen and Williams, 2006). A detailed introduction to GPR can be found in Rasmussen and Williams (2006). To predict outputs from new input variables where no observations are available, a function is to be found. A prior Gaussian distribution of expected probable functions is defined before any observations are seen. These functions have a zero mean and covariance matrix which is calculated using a covariance function. The covariance function also called the kernel, sets the specification of the prior distribution and is the key factor of a Gaussian process. Different functions are available and are tuned by their hyperparameters which, e.g., describe the similarity between input samples. Thus, also the hyperparameters, and assumptions about noise define the prior. Adding the data to the prior gives the posterior distribution of functions, defining the mean function fitting the data. Finally, the mean function and the covariance function completely identify a Gaussian process (Rasmussen and Williams, 2006).

The advantage of the GPR is that resulting from the Bayesian approach also the probability of a prediction value is given. These uncertainty estimates together with the availability of different covariance functions make it a more transparent machine-learning model (Upreti et al., 2019). The hyperparameters are estimated from the data using a maximum likelihood approach, which is done by inverting the kernel matrix (Gram matrix) that contains the covariance functions over all input variables. Due to the inversion of the matrix the complexity of a Gaussian process is the quadratic of the number of observations which makes the model training for large datasets with more than 5,000 observations very time-consuming or even unreasonable without approximating it (Berger et al., 2021; Rasmussen and Williams, 2006; Verrelst et al., 2016). On the other hand, GPR performs well with small datasets as it has flexible kernels and recognises useful observations from the training dataset (Lazaro-Gredilla et al., 2014).

Different kernel functions $k(x_i, x_j)$ are available, for example, the squared exponential, also called the radial basis function (RBF) kernel, the Matérn, the rational quadratic or the polynomial kernel. They can be combined to fit the data (Rasmussen and Williams, 2006). The

kernels used here are the RBF given in (2) plus an independent noise kernel (3) as done in Castelli et al. (2023) and Verrelst et al. (2012).

$$k(x_i, x_j) = \exp\left(-\frac{d(x_i, x_j)^2}{2l^2}\right) + \sigma_n^2 \quad (2)$$

The RBF (2) is a stationary (invariant to changes in the input space) and smooth kernel, its hyperparameter is the length scale ($l > 0$) which controls the smoothness of the function. $d(x_i, x_j)$ is the Euclidian distance between two data points. If l is a scalar, the kernel is isotropic and assumes the same similarity over all observations. If l is a vector with the same number as observations, the kernel becomes anisotropic, thus acknowledging if the distances between observations differ across dimensions. The WhiteKernel (3) independently estimates the noise of the data with the hyperparameter `noise_level`, the variance of the normally distributed, global noise σ_n^2 (scikit-learn, 2024b).

$$k(x_i, x_j) = \sigma_n^2 \text{ if } x_i == x_j \text{ else } 0 \quad (3)$$

2.3.1.3 CatBoost

The Categorical Boosting (CatBoost) is a gradient-boosting ensemble algorithm and library developed by Prokhorenkova et al. (2017). In gradient boosting, an ensemble predictor is constructed by using gradients (partial derivatives) of the loss function to iteratively find suitable candidates to be added to the ensemble of decision trees (Hancock and Khoshgoftaar, 2020; Prokhorenkova et al., 2017). The CatBoost has two improvements to this approach which consist of the usage of ordered boosting through permutation and the possibility to process categorical features, also by combining them to additional features (Prokhorenkova et al., 2017). The decision trees are full binary, symmetrical trees which reduces overfitting and improves the generalization and precision of the CatBoost (Hancock and Khoshgoftaar, 2020; Luo et al., 2021).

Hancock and Khoshgoftaar (2020) noted that the CatBoost is best suited for heterogeneous data, especially if categorical features are present. It is sensible to hyperparameters which makes it important to tune them (ibid.). As the features used here are all numerical the maximum number of combinations of categorical features is not important. The other hyperparameters tuned here are the depth of the tree (`depth`) and the maximum number of trees in the ensemble (`iterations`). The learning rate (`learning_rate`) is set automatically (CatBoost, n.d.).

2.3.2 MODEL SELECTION

The model selection consists of the model training of the four regressors on the different input feature sets: Just the S1 features and S1 plus all possible combinations of the auxiliary DOY, meteorological data, and class. This way, the potential of S1 for the estimation of LAI can be evaluated and auxiliary features as well as the best-suited modelling approach can be identified.

To improve the regressor's performances feature selection and hyperparameter optimisation is done during model selection. The models are evaluated using the accuracy metrics (2.4.1) and the computational time required for the model selection. The hardware used for model training has 126 GM RAM on a 32-core processor with a maximum speed of 2.48 GHz. The selected features are compared according to their rank of importance over the different models. The four best-performing among the 32 models are selected for the gap-filling of the test-set in 2023 (2.4.4) and the ground measurements (2.4.5).

Cross-validation is used in the different steps of the model selection to prevent the models from overfitting. This would happen during the feature selection if the variables were selected without cross-validation (cf. Meyer et al., 2018). The time series cross-validation accounts for the autocorrelation of observations near in time in evaluating the model on future samples. However with every fold data is added to the first set so that successive folds are not independent of previous ones (scikit-learn, 2024c). Ideally, also the location should be considered in the cross-validation (Meyer et al., 2018), though there is no implementation in scikit-learn available yet.

2.3.2.1 Feature Selection

In the first step, for each model, the best-performing features for every feature set are selected. Feature selection is done to enhance the models' performance by removing deceptive features and at the same time avoiding redundant or useless features. This reduces the time required for model training and provides a deeper understanding of the data (Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003; scikit-learn, 2024d). The feature selection is done using a recursive feature elimination with a 5-fold time series cross-validation within a pipeline. During the recursive feature elimination, the least performing features are eliminated with the step size set to one, thus features are removed one by one until no further increase in the selected ranking criterion, here R^2 (2.4.1), is observed (Guyon et al., 2002). The RFE is effective and the most common method for feature selection (Kuhn and Johnson, 2020). E.g., Luo et al. (2021) found a significant enhancement in the prediction of AGB using the RFE. And even if like for Xu et al. (2022) the RFE does not improve the accuracy, it still reduces the input features.

The pipeline allows scaling the input features of each split independently to avoid information on the whole data or training set leaking into the training of the model. The minimum number of features to be selected is one. The model internal feature importance is used, or in the case of GPR and LR permutation importance helps in the RFECV as they have no internal feature importance. This procedure is done for all five cross-validation sets and the selection is based on the average over all folds (scikit-learn, 2024d).

2.3.2.2 Hyperparameter Optimisation

After the selection of the features, the hyperparameters are optimized. Ideally, one could evaluate the best hyperparameters for every input feature combination to select the model on the finest scale. This is computationally expensive thus this step is done afterwards, and the default parameters used in the feature selection are supposed to be sufficient.

To test multiple sets of parameters and cross-validate them, scikit-learns GridSearchCV is used (scikit-learn, 2024b). As GPR comes with an automatic hyperparameter optimisation and LR does not have hyperparameters they are not tuned. In preliminary tests, tuning the `n_estimators` of RF with 300 or 500 estimators instead of the default one hundred resulted in a model taking up three or five times more storage with increases of accuracies less than 1%. Thus, only CatBoost is tuned. The grid of the hyperparameters is given in Table 2. Investigated parameter values are based on preliminary tests as well as on CatBoost (n.d.) and Zhang et al. (2020). Again, the above-introduced time series 5-fold cross-validation is used.

Table 2 Hyperparameters tuned for each model.

Model	Library	Hyperparameter	Investigated parameter values
LR	Scikit-learn	-	-
RF	Scikit-learn	<code>n_estimators</code>	Default=100
GPR	Scikit-learn	length scale	Automatic hyperparameter optimisation
CatBoost	catboost	iterations	[1000, 1500, 2000]
		depth	[5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10]

2.4 VALIDATION

The model selection step (2.3.2) is based on the validation metrics described in 2.4.1. The prediction and validation for the test-set 2023 (2.4.4) and the ground measurements (2.4.5) are based on these metrics too. Additionally, the correlation between yield and LAI measured in the field (2.4.2) and the estimation of field LAI from S2 LAI is assessed (2.4.3).

2.4.1 VALIDATION METRICS

The following performance metrics are used to verify the correlation of LAI with the S2 LAI as well as to determine the performance of the regression models: The coefficient of determination R^2 (4), the mean absolute error MAE (5), the root mean squared error $RMSE$ (6), the mean bias $Bias$ (7) and the total time for model training including the feature selection and eventual hyperparameter optimisation in seconds are measured. The unit of the MAE, RMSE, and bias is m^2m^{-2} as for the LAI and is not stated separately below for reasons of readability.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (4)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (5)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (6)$$

$$Bias = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)}{N} \quad (7)$$

Where \hat{y}_i is the predicted LAI using the test input features. y_i is the observed S2 LAI of the test set and \bar{y} is the mean of the observed values. N is the number of observations.

2.4.2 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN IN-SITU LAI AND YIELD

To confirm the usage of LAI as a proxy for yield, the in-situ measurements are correlated. As the yield and LAI are not normally distributed, have potential outliers, and their relationship is not linear, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient ρ (8) and the squared ρ^2 are used. For comparison with Castelli et al. (2023) who used Pearson's correlation coefficient, also the latter is computed. Note here, that ρ^2 refers to correlations between two variables whereas the coefficient of determination R^2 is used for correlations from multiple predictors, e.g., from regression models and targets the correlation between the observed y and the predicted \hat{y} .

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6 \sum (R_i - S_i)^2}{N(N^2 - 1)} \quad (8)$$

Where R_i and S_i are the ranks of the in-situ LAI and yield.

2.4.3 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SENTINEL-2 AND IN-SITU LAI

The relationship between the S2 and the in-situ LAI is supposed to be linear and, thus is investigated using a linear correlation. As no regression model is applied here, the Pearson correlation coefficient (r), its square (r^2) and the validation metrics in 2.4.1 are used for the validation. This follows the proceedings of Castelli et al. (2023), though no 5 m buffer is used to extract the S2 LAI as the samples were taken in the centre of an S2 pixel. The maximum time difference between in-situ LAI and S2 LAI is five days with no mowing event between the dates. For both, the correlation with yield and the S2 LAI, the effect of lodged vegetation is assessed.

2.4.4 VALIDATION ON THE TEST-SET FOR 2023

The best-performing models and features are selected and applied on the test-set containing unseen meadows to gap-fill missing LAI values for 2023. The predicted LAI is consequently validated against the observed S2 LAI using the validation metrics to get the accuracy of the gap-filled maps. Additionally, the results are assessed for every altitudinal class.

2.4.5 VALIDATION AGAINST THE IN-SITU DATA

For the reason of an independent validation dataset, also the eight meadows where field data was collected are not part of the database for model training. This allows us to validate the model performance to the S2 LAI and the LAI in-situ measurements collected here. Again, the validation metrics are used to compare the predicted and observed LAI, for every single meadow and meadow class. However, the validation meadows only represent a fraction of the study area and are spatially clustered and bi-weekly available. Thus, the accuracy of the models for these specific meadows could be different than for the whole of 2023.

3 RESULTS

3.1 VERIFICATION OF THE IN-SITU MEASUREMENTS

The Spearman's rank correlation ρ between the in-situ LAI and yield is 0.82, strongly positive and significant. Using Pearson's correlation coefficient gives $r=0.64$ and $r^2=0.42$. The low yield is slightly overestimated, and the high yield of the mostly lodged vegetation is strongly underestimated. LAI increases faster than yield and the linear regression line with the 95% confidence interval as visible in Figure 8 indicates a non-linear, exponential relationship. Lodging leads to higher yields at lower LAI. Thus, removing the lodged observations results in a reduction of the slope and an increase of ρ to 0.86 and $\rho^2=0.75$ ($r=0.71$, $r^2=0.50$).

Figure 8 Correlation of in-situ LAI and yield depending on lodging.

The r^2 for the correlation between S2 LAI and in-situ LAI is 0.61 and the RMSE=1.99. The in-situ LAI reaches values above eight and high values are strongly underestimated by the S2 LAI. Thus, the mean bias is -1.4. Removing observations where lodging occurred (see Figure 9a) results in a slight increase in r^2 , and a reduction of the RMSE and bias. Lodged vegetation is thus observed similarly by S2 though adds noise. Comparing the single meadows in Figure 9b (metrics are given in Appendix B) reveals a general underestimation over the whole range of in-situ LAI by S2 LAI for F1, F2, and L2 which results in strong negative mean bias. For the

other meadows high LAI is underestimated and low LAI is slightly overestimated. R1 bears the strongest underestimation of high in-situ LAI and is the meadow with the lowest r^2 (0.38). F1, L1, and L2 instead reach a higher r^2 of up to 0.9.

Figure 9 Correlation between in-situ LAI and S2 LAI. a) for all meadows and b) per single meadow.

Removing the lodged observations increases the correlation between S2 LAI and in-situ LAI or reduces it by a maximum of 0.04 in r^2 , except for R1. The biggest difference between the LAI values in R1 is identified for the beginning of May. Visual investigations show that the S2 scene from 06.05.2023 that is used for the correlation with the in-situ observations from 08.05.2023 has a complex cloud pattern over the Ritten and is not correctly masked. This way, cloud shadow affects the estimation of LAI on R1 and R5, slight cloud coverage can be observed for R4 and just R3 has clear conditions. Removing this single observation increases the r^2 from 0.38 to 0.62 and the RMSE is reduced from 2.29 to 1.63 for R1. Also, R5's values improve slightly ($r^2=0.64$, RMSE=1.89).

3.2 MODEL SELECTION

The different models' performance is assessed using the validation set and is shown in Table 3 (full table in Appendix C). For two models, namely the RF and CatBoost, using all features provides the best performance. The R^2 is the highest, and RMSE and MAE are the lowest using these features. GPR yields the best results in only relying on the S1 features and the DOY. LR performs best using S1, meteorological data, and the class and gets the same values using all features but the DOY is deselected in the RFECV which means that the two models are identical. RF on all features is the most accurate model of all when applied on the validation set, it results in R^2 of 0.70 and RMSE of 0.97 after 53.5 mins of training. CatBoost follows with $R^2=0.54$ and an RMSE=1.20 and about 16 min shorter training time than RF. The optimized hyperparameters of CatBoost have a depth of ten at two thousand iterations. GPR is the third and has R^2 of 0.28, RMSE of 1.51, and requires the longest fitting time with almost 1.5 hours. The least accurate is LR with $R^2=0.15$ and RMSE=1.64 after 1.5 minutes of training and feature selection.

Table 3 Performance of the selected models after feature selection and hyperparameter optimisation.

Model	Features	R^2	RMSE	MAE	Bias	Time [hh:mm:ss]	Hyper-parameter
LR	S1, meteo, class	0.15	1.64	1.31	0.00	00:01:29	
RF	all	0.70	0.97	0.68	0.02	00:53:32	
GPR	S1, DOY	0.28	1.51	1.17	-0.03	01:29:15	
CatBoost	all	0.54	1.20	0.90	0.00	00:37:20	10; 2000

Using S1 as the only feature set yields the lowest R^2 and highest RMSE values when comparing all feature sets (see Figure 10). Adding the class as a second feature to S1 increases the accuracy slightly but with a much stronger effect if instead the DOY is added. In the mean, adding the DOY as an auxiliary feature improves the R^2 by 0.31 in CatBoost and by 0.32 in RF. The RMSE and MAE are reduced by 0.31 to 0.33. The meteorological data gives plus 0.23 in the R^2 of CatBoost and 0.34 of RF in the mean. The class provides the lowest increase of accuracy when added, 0.02 for CatBoost and 0.03 increase of R^2 in RF. The RMSE and MAE decrease similarly. GPR only profits from the DOY in the case of using S1 and DOY, the other features are not advantageous. The accuracy of LR only benefits from the meteorological data that adds 0.08 to the R^2 in the mean. This way, especially for RF and CatBoost, the added value is the most when adding the DOY, with meteorological data and the class following second and third.

Figure 10 Comparison of the model performance according to feature sets.

The selected features for the single best-performing models are depicted in Figure 11. The LR selects different features and evaluates their importance differing from the three non-linear regressors. Here, the auxiliary features are the most important given they occupy the highest ranks with DOY taking the first place. RF and CatBoost keep all auxiliary features and only eliminate single S1 features. The temperature is ranked second in RF and CatBoost, thus more important than the precipitation which is similarly important as the class.

Figure 11 Selected features with ranking according to importance.

GPR keeps the ascending product as the only S1 feature. RF is left with more so that it uses both VH and VV polarisations and the square difference and product in both orbits plus the ascending ratio and the descending difference. For RF, the S1 indices have lower importance than the polarisations. CatBoost eliminates all features except the VH and VV in ascending and VV and square difference in descending, thus prefers the VV polarisations. The models consent that the RVI, sum, VH product, and sum/product are not used for the prediction of LAI. The VV, the VH, and the product in ascending instead, and the square difference and VV in descending orbit are selected in multiple models.

3.3 VALIDATION ON THE TEST-SET FOR 2023

The results for the model validation on the unseen meadows in 2023, also according to the altitudinal classes, are displayed in Figure 12. The whole table can be found in Appendix D. Apart from a few exceptions, the models perform poorly overall. When considering all meadows, CatBoost yields the best results with $R^2=0.16$ and $RMSE=1.34$, followed by GPR ($R^2=0.11$, $RMSE=1.37$). The other models, LR and RF do not reach positive R^2 and are thus insufficiently performing on the test set. Particularly LR has extremely high RMSE.

Divided into the different classes, GPR achieves the highest R^2 of 0.32 and lowest RMSE of 1.27 in the south-facing “Subalpine and upper montane” class. CatBoost performs similar ($R^2=0.29$, $RMSE=1.30$). The second-best class is the north-facing Lower montane class, in which RF, scoring better only in the north-facing classes, marginally outperforms GPR and CatBoost ($R^2=0.27$, $RMSE=1.28$). CatBoost is the only model with an R^2 of over 0.07 consistently in all classes, while the other models perform very poorly in some cases.

Plotting the predicted LAI against the S2 LAI in Figure 13 reveals more details regarding residuals deviating from the S2 LAI and distinctive prediction patterns. The plots consist of a random sample of five hundred observations drawn from the 290,000 predictions made for the unseen meadows in 2023. LR strongly underestimates the S2 LAI which is observable in the points above the dashed line representing perfect predictions. Most of the values predicted by LR are zero or even negative, which should not be the case. The other models tend to slightly overestimate the LAI and just predict positive LAI values. In particular, the residuals for high LAI values are the largest, so that RF, for example, predicts an LAI of 3 for an S2 LAI of 7. CatBoost, RF, and GPR do not predict above 5 and GPR even makes a sharp cut for values above around 3.8.

Figure 12 Validation for the test set according to altitudinal classes. Negative R^2 are shown as zero and values outside the plotted area are indicated by arrows.

For CatBoost and RF two clusters can be identified causing a gap in the prediction of LAI=2. GPR shows the most distinctive pattern as it predicts just certain values. This results in multiple elongated accumulations of predictions across the y-direction until the mentioned sudden stop. The time required for prediction is given in Figure 13 too. As in training the models, GPR takes the longest for predicting (21.7 s), whereas the other models take less than one second.

Figure 13 Validation against S2 LAI and residuals.

3.4 VALIDATION AGAINST THE IN-SITU MEASUREMENTS

The predicted LAI is evaluated over the eight meadows on which in situ measurements were conducted for the year 2023. Figure 14 shows the result of the validation against the in-situ and S2 LAI of all and the single meadows. The table with the full results can be found in Appendix E. R3 and L2 are small meadows and due to buffering, the number of overlaying field observations is further reduced so that not enough in-situ observations can be used for a reasonable validation. The performance of all models is better when validated against the S2 LAI as the R^2 is higher and the RMSE (in columns) is lower than for the in-situ LAI. The R^2 is mostly negative (shown as 0) or close to zero and the RMSE lays over 1.5 which means that the model performs very poorly. Only for F1 and L1 when validated against the S2 LAI the results are better with positive R^2 . For F1 the RF reaches an $R^2=0.61$ and $RMSE=0.82$ and is closely followed by GPR ($R^2=0.58$, $RMSE=0.85$) with a slightly lower bias. Over L1 GPR is the best with $R^2=0.55$ and $RMSE=1.01$, followed by RF ($R^2=0.51$, $RMSE=1.05$). In both cases, CatBoost is the third and LR the least performing model.

Figure 14 Validation against the in-situ and S2 LAI.

Figure 15 for single altitudinal classes (full table in Appendix F) shows that the models only perform for the south-facing Colline class. GPR reaches the best results with $R^2=0.22$ and $RMSE=1.14$ for this class against S2 LAI. RF follows with $R^2=0.19$ and $RMSE=1.16$. Three-quarters of the observations in this class originate from F1 which yields the best performance as revealed above. In all other classes and against the in-situ LAI the models are again not performant so R^2 has no positive values and the RMSE is high.

Figure 15 Validation against the in-situ and S2 LAI according to altitudinal classes.

Figure 16 shows the time series of the predicted LAI against the in-situ and S2 LAI for the meadow F1 on which the models perform best. This allows inspecting the predicted LAI regarding the mowing practices on this meadow. It is evident that both S2 underestimates the in-situ LAI as stated above, and the models underestimate the S2 LAI. The time series pattern of the LAI increases until the single mowing events, with the first growing phase having the highest LAI values. The high in-situ values before the hay cut are due to medium and strong lodging, as are the values before the last cut. The models capture this pattern up to the first mowing event. However, all models except GPR predict a lower LAI after an initial increase in the first two observations. Thereafter, LR and GPR show difficulties in predicting the decline in LAI after the cuts which is delayed in the case of CatBoost. Matching the best metrics stated above, the RF captures the mowing events the best. However, comparing the time series plots for the other meadows in Appendix G visually, shows that the same prediction pattern is used for all meadows and coincidentally matches better in the case of RF and F1.

Especially for LR the range of predicted values throughout the growing season and on single days is very narrow. The same can be observed in the exemplary map for F1 on 08.09.2023 in Figure 17. The S2 LAI ranges from 2.7 to 4.7 and the in-situ LAI is slightly higher. The values are higher in the central, northwestern part of the meadow. GPR predicts LAI between 3.2 and 3.4 and does not grasp the spatial pattern indicated by S2. LR is similar, though predicts a slightly lower LAI. Only RF and CatBoost distinguish spatially, have a wider range of predicted LAI, and give higher values in the centre of the meadow.

Figure 16 Time series of the predicted LAI, in-situ, and S2 LAI exemplarily for F1 and the respective mowing events.

Figure 17 Exemplary spatial prediction for F1 on 08.09.2023.
Background imagery: Google, © 2024 Maxar Technologies.

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 GROUND MEASUREMENTS

Regarding the relation between in-situ LAI and yield, the coefficient of correlation ($r^2=0.66$, without lodging $r^2=0.71$) for 2021 reported in Castelli et al. (2023), is slightly lower than the ρ^2 but higher than the r^2 in this study for 2023. The faster increase in LAI is observed too (Castelli et al., 2023) though the relation shown in the respective graphs indicates a linear relationship (cf. *ibid.*). In contrast to that, in the present study, a non-linear relationship is found, which is supported by the better performance of Spearman's rank correlation. The overestimation of low yield stated by Castelli et al. (2023) too, could be because yield is retrieved from 5 cm above ground, whereas LAI is measured close to the ground. This way LAI of short grass can still be measured whereas the yield is close to 0 t/ha. Using an exponential relationship between yield and LAI could reduce the perception of overestimation and fit a later increase in yield in comparison to LAI.

High yield instead is underestimated, mainly due to the negative effect of lodging (cf. Castelli et al., 2023). Measuring the LAI in lodged areas correctly is challenging. As the vegetation lies flat on the ground, the LAI is measured considering the part of the vegetation horizontally above the sensor, while the other parts of the grass stems are outside the sensor's field of view and therefore not included. Hence, sampling in these areas is not recommended, or the samples must be excluded as suggested in Castelli et al. (2023) and LI-COR (2023). For this reason, no sampling should be conducted in lodged areas during future field campaigns.

The relationship between S2 LAI and in-situ LAI for all meadows is $r^2=0.61$ and comparable to the validation of Brown et al. (2021), who yielded $r^2=0.63$ over various grassland and herbaceous sites throughout the United States but much lower bias (0.16). Castelli et al. (2023), determined a better correlation ($r^2=0.78$) with a lower RMSE and bias for the same meadows in 2021 than here. When looking at single meadows, the r^2 was comparably high or even higher for F1, L1, L2, and R3 than in 2021. Lodging can explain the differences for R4. The strong reduction in r^2 for R1 is probably due to wrongly masked cloud shadow in the early growing period. R5 was not sampled in 2021 yet though is also influenced by that. This means, that the estimation of LAI from S2 in comparison to in-situ measurements is potentially influenced by lodging, and clouds or cloud shadows that are still present even if the data was masked. Especially for high values, the S2- is lower than the in-situ LAI.

F2's range of LAI is smaller than for the other meadows and has the highest ratio of graminoids (>95%, as in 2021, Castelli et al., 2023). It was mowed four times instead of two times in 2021 whereas the mowing frequency of the other meadows did a maximum change by one. Potentially, the meadow was highly managed and reseeded before the growing season of 2023

to enhance the production which could explain the increase in cuts per year (cf. Vogel et al., 2012). Additional comments during the field measurements reveal that F2 has patches with higher or lower vegetation and management traces from tractors are visible. The already dense, clay-rich Terra fusca of F2 (cf. Amelung et al., 2018) is probably compacted by the heavy tractors which hinders plant growth in the track lines. It is not clear whether this has been the case in 2021 too though could imply that management activities potentially alter the estimation of LAI from S2.

Against the in-situ LAI, the models are not performing and underestimate the values by far. This could be due to the case that they are solely trained on S2 LAI, which does have a good relationship with the in-situ LAI though underestimates it as well. For future validation using the in-situ measurements, one could apply a constant to normalise the in-situ LAI with the S2 values. Also, the r^2 could be investigated instead of the R^2 , so that the validation relies on a correlation and not on the exact prediction of in-situ LAI. Additionally, for some meadows, too few observations are present for a reliable validation of the predicted LAI. Particularly small meadows lack validation pairs between predicted and in-situ LAI due to the buffering. A solution to that could be to sample in bigger meadows only and apply a buffer for the field measurements as well to avoid the influence of mixed pixels. Otherwise, one could use the closest in-situ observations for predicted pixels in small meadows and not match them on exact coordinates. However, this could imply that potential spatial variations within the meadow influence the results.

4.2 BEST-SUITED REGRESSION MODELS

The validation of the LAI predictions for 2020-2022 from the models reveals the RF as the best-performing regression model for the estimation of LAI from S1 in Alpine grasslands for the investigated meadows. It can explain 70% of the variance and has the lowest RMSE of all models. CatBoost performs second best while GPR is less powerful and takes the longest for the model training. The LR benchmark fails, confirming that the relationship between the LAI biophysical parameter and the SAR signal and indices is non-linear. This means that the more complex and time-consuming non-linear regression algorithms are beneficial for estimating grassland LAI.

However, the test on unseen meadows shows that all models are barely better than random predictions. The performance over the eight forage production meadows is even worse, probably because they only represent a fraction of the study area, are spatially clustered and the validation data is only bi-weekly available. Since the test for 2023 refers to observations temporally and spatially outside the training and validation data, this is an independent stress

test for the transferability and robustness of the models. The implication is that the models work well on the meadows and in the years for which they were trained. Nevertheless, they are not robust and reliable enough to be applied everywhere and at any time in the study area. In more detail, the test on the unseen meadows in 2023 and on the in-situ measurements denies RF as the best-performing model and instead, CatBoost and GPR are favoured.

4.2.1 GAUSSIAN PROCESS REGRESSOR

This is surprising in the case of GPR as it has a worse performance in the validation than the ensemble models. In testing, GPR loses less R^2 and RMSE than the other models, which could imply that it is less overfitted and more robust when applied temporally and spatially outside the training data. The performance of GPR seems unsatisfactory but is applied here to a bigger area of interest than in comparison to other studies. For example, Castelli et al. (2023), tested S1 σ° VV, VH, ratio, and RVI with auxiliary features (SMC and DOY) for gap-filling in S2 LAI over 118 grassland plots using a GPR. The 5-fold cross-validation gave $R^2=0.83$ and $RMSE=0.25$ with the best predictors being VH, SM, and DOY. An additional test where locations were left out achieved $R^2=0.53$ at maximum, with $RMSE=0.66$ (Castelli et al., 2023). This can be compared to the test for unseen meadows in 2023 and the in-situ measurements and GPR reaching R^2 up to 0.58 against S2 over F1, thus revealing that the results of this thesis are in line with previous, smaller-scale applications.

The estimation of in-situ LAI of three wheat parcels in Brittany, France, by Mercier et al. (2020) from S1 σ° with a GPR achieved $R^2=0.91$. Estimating LAI of rape parcels from VV after the 10 times repeated 3-fold cross-validation was less performant ($R^2=0.36$) (Mercier et al., 2020). Pipia et al. (2019), instead estimated the S2 LAI of different crop types over a homogenous study area of 140 km² and flat terrain of Castile and León, Spain, using S1 σ° RVI (temporally smoothed at the pixel level). For a 50-day time gap over all crop types, their GPR achieved $R^2=0.68$ and for 140 days 0.12, with $RMSE=1.09$. The Multioutput Gaussian Process (MOGP) improved the prediction ($R^2=0.74$ for 50 days, $R^2=0.33$, $RMSE=0.50$ for 140 days) so that the authors suggest using MOGP especially when treating long time gaps (Pipia et al., 2019). They also indicated a crop type called forage crops which assumably include grasslands. The coverage of this type is marginal and GPR achieved $R^2=0.06$ and MOGP $R^2=0.31$ for the respective 140-day gap. The results of Pipia et al. (2019) for the long-time gap, resemble the validation against 2023 in this study even if covering different crop types, also with similar accuracy.

In conclusion, considering that the study areas of Pipia et al. (2019) and Mercier et al. (2020) are more homogenous and of flat terrain and the one of Castelli et al. (2023) is of smaller size, the performance of GPR here is comparable. In the future, active learning should be

implemented to enhance the performance of GPR by selecting the most useful observations for the model training. However, it must be considered that GPR takes a long time and much RAM for training on a fraction of the input data. Thus, GPR is not recommended unreservedly for the modelling of LAI of Alpine grassland. The usage of a MOGP is to be investigated in the future and will potentially enhance the performance in the heterogenous study area of the Alps.

4.2.2 CATBOOST

The CatBoost algorithm is evaluated for the first time for grassland LAI gap-filling using S1 in this study and its performance is promising. It is lower than RF in the validation but outperforms RF and GPR in the test, although the performance of all models in the latter is not satisfying. The fact that CatBoost performs better than other models was also the case in other applications, e.g., for wheat yield prediction from S1 and S2 in northern Spain (Uribeetxebarria et al., 2023) or in estimating forest AGB from optical Landsat data in the Chinese province Jinlin (Luo et al., 2021). Here, CatBoost outperformed RF by a slight increase in R^2 (CatBoost $R^2=0.73$, RF $R^2=0.72$) and requiring less time for training (ibid.). Zhang et al., 2020, also achieved comparable results between RF ($R^2=0.70$) and CatBoost ($R^2=0.72$) for global forest AGB estimation from multiple satellite data.

In contrast to that, the results here are less accurate. Also, the lower performance in the validation and the usage of optical data in the studies just mentioned could imply that CatBoost is not as well suited for the gap-filling of S2 LAI using S1. It is possible that the hyperparameters are not perfect, which Hancock and Khoshgoftaar (2020) described as crucial for the application of CatBoost. Consequently, the other hyperparameters such as the learning rate which is set automatically should be investigated in future research.

4.2.3 RANDOM FOREST REGRESSOR

The RF leaves the validation with a promising R^2 of 0.70 and RMSE below 1 though cannot hold the expectations in the independent test and fails for the unseen meadows in 2023. Only over F1 RF can explain 61% of the variance of the S2 LAI which is the highest result in the test. Studies estimating grassland LAI from S1 using RF report the regressor to be failing similarly as it was found in this study in the test on the unseen meadows: Raab et al. (2020), investigated the usage of S1 σ° , VV, and VH to estimate in-situ grassland forage quantity and quality in a study area of 230 km² in the north-east of Bavaria, Germany, using RF and achieved a maximum R^2 of 0.12 for S1 features after a 100 times repeated 10-fold cross-validation (Raab et al., 2020). Wang (2019) predicted in-situ LAI of two pasture sites in Oklahoma, USA, for 2016 from models trained on 2015. Using an RF model with VV and VH σ° polarisations resulted in a correlation coefficient $r=0.04$ with an RMSE of 1.42. LR and SVM performed more favourably, though the number of observations was very small (Wang, 2019).

A study with better results was conducted by Martinez et al. (2021) to estimate mangrove forest LAI from S1 for a small area in Kawit, Philippines. The σ° backscatter coefficients of VV and VH and the ratio, RVI, difference, and the polarisation mean (sum/2) were utilized to predict S2 LAI. The RF model achieved up to $R^2=0.89$ and $RMSE=0.28$ for 2016 (Martinez et al., 2021). However, it must be noted that the area is small and no information on the validation is given. In this way, an appropriate comparison with the estimation of grassland LAI in this study is not possible.

The conclusion is that RF is also not ideal for estimating the LAI of grassland. It shows strengths in predicting some individual meadows and has a similar short training time as CatBoost but seems to be overfitted to 2020-2022. Thus, the symmetric trees resulting from CatBoost's gradient boosting could be an advantage over the randomness in RF's bagging method.

4.3 BEST-SUITED FEATURES

The key features for the estimation of grassland LAI in North-Eastern Italy are the DOY, temperature, precipitation, and altitudinal class followed by the S1 features, with ascending VV and VH and descending square difference. This confirms the reporting by Holtgrave et al. (2020) and Pipia et al. (2019) of the SAR signal being challenging to interpret without additional information as it is altered by different surface properties. Also, the statement of Hobohm et al. (2021) regarding the impact of driving climatic variables on grassland productivity can be supported.

4.3.1 SENTINEL-1 FEATURES

The S1 polarisations and indices are the least important feature set for the investigated models. The drawback in the importance of the S1 features and the low accuracy when training the models without auxiliary predictors can be found in other studies too. For example, Raab et al. (2020) ascribed the low importance of S1 for the prediction of grassland yield quantity and quality in their models to the C-band sensor's wavelength of about 5 cm and pointed out to rather use the even shorter wavelength of X-band SAR.

On the other hand, the RTC product used here is supposed to achieve better results than the GRD as suggested by Flores-Anderson et al. (2023). This could imply limitations in the preprocessing already mentioned in the methodology (2.2.2): Against the instructions by Small (2011), the RTC from the Microsoft Planetary Computer is derived from σ° and not β° backscatter. It is not clear if the performance would increase using another initial product and no comparable study using the same product could be identified. An option would be to use

the analysis-ready S1 normalized backscatter (NRB) by ESA (European Space Agency, n.d.) in the future which is currently under development and represents RTC γ° backscatter derived from S1 SLC IW or EW mode.

Another reason could be the complex terrain of the Alps which may still influence the geometry of the RTC data even after the corrections. For example, slopes affected by foreshortening are corrected and the available data is “stretched” to cover the whole slope. This way, the radiometric resolution of the data cannot be recovered fully to provide the same detail as if sensed without geometric and radiometric distortions. Modelling the LAI of Alpine grasslands on such slopes from S1 might be more difficult. A solution could be to account for the usefulness of corrected foreshortening in omitting meadows past a certain threshold of slope and avoiding distortions too big and still present after the RTC.

Furthermore, the usage of both ascending and descending orbits as separate features for the same day can be contradictory as they are not sensed by the same sensor at the same time. With the loss of S1 B, the temporal resolution of the mission is only half and provides an acquisition only every six to seven days for the orbits respectively. This way, the temporal difference between an ascending and a descending acquisition can be up to three days and the temporal resolution now is too low to fill all gaps in S2 with this approach. As explained earlier, the orbits could be merged into one feature as done by Pipia et al. (2019) for a topographically plainer study area. This would not only increase the temporal coverage of S1 data but also avoid merging ascending and descending sensed more than one day apart.

In the case of an ascending and descending acquisition on the same day, the data could be merged after previously determining their correlation. The threshold for very steep slopes mentioned above could also be applied as well as using the available data of the other acquisition in case of radar shadow. A label of the orbit direction could serve as an auxiliary feature. Yet, the study by Holtgrave et al. (2020) did not profit from this when investigating a multiple LR between S1 and S2 vegetation indices for different agricultural land use types (amongst them also grassland) in Lower Saxony, Germany.

The speckle filtering after the orthorectification could result in misleading smoothness as geometric units are already altered by resampling and reprojecting. In other studies, the data is not only spatially but also temporally filtered to reduce noise: For example, Caballero et al. (2022) increased the performance of the estimation of wheat LAI from S1 with a GPR by using the optimized Whittaker smoother from S1 acquisitions at different local incidence angles and from different orbits for a small study area in the Buenos Aires Province, Argentina. Even if the usage of RTC should not require that, the usage in the mountainous terrain of the Alps could still reveal differences and the models profit from the filtering.

Single features of S1 are kept in the RFECV of multiple models and are thus more suited for the estimation of Alpine grassland LAI from S1 than others. This is the VV, VH, and the product in ascending, the square difference, and VV in descending orbit that achieved promising results for multiple models. RF consents to the studies of Castelli et al. (2023), Crabbe et al. (2019), and Wang (2019) that reported VH to perform better than VV. However, CatBoost prefers the VV in both orbits and performs better than RF, thus does not fully support the volume scattering as the best S1 indicator for LAI.

The RVI and ratio which combine the volume scattering and the vegetation water content in using both polarisations are not useful features in this study as except for the ascending ratio in RF they were not kept during the RFECV. This contradicts the recommendations of Holtgrave et al. (2020) and Kumar et al. (2013) to use the RVI for agricultural vegetation monitoring. However, Castelli et al. (2023) also found the VH more suitable than RVI for the estimation of LAI from S1 in Alpine grasslands. The sum and the difference of VV and VH which is well-performing when used for the estimation of forest and maize AGB by Laurin et al. (2018) and Xu et al. (2022) can only partially be recommended for grassland LAI as only the descending difference was kept in the RF as third best of 10 kept S1 features. Amongst the recently developed indices by Xu et al. (2022) (the product, VH/product, sum/product, and square difference), only the square difference and the product can be suggested as advantageous in this study. Especially in the GPR, the ascending product is important and the only other kept feature except from the DOY. The square difference has lower importance than the polarisations for RF and CatBoost and is thus probably only helpful to increase the distinction between them but losing physical meaning.

Regarding further processing of S1 with special attention to the importance of the precipitation data and the result achieved by Castelli et al. (2023) in including SMC data, the SAR signal could be decomposed to separate the vegetation backscattering from the ground scattering component (Tsokas et al., 2022). This could be done using the H/A/ α polarimetric decomposition by Cloude and Pottier (1996) to determine the type of scattering. Harfenmeister et al. (2021) achieved high R^2 values for the estimation of wheat LAI ($R^2=0.67$) and even higher values for plant height and other vegetation biophysical parameters using VH, VV, entropy, and α from S1 in multiple linear regression for small test sites in Northeast Germany. Nasirzadehdizaji et al. (2019) also found high r^2 for α when linearly correlated against wheat height for a small test site in central Turkey, though the sum of VV and VH, and VV performed better. Despite the decomposition being more favourable for the estimation of vegetation height than LAI and its application in grasslands so far only tested for mowing event detection (Reinermann et al., 2022), the usage of polarimetric SAR could be investigated in the future.

4.3.2 METEOROLOGICAL DATA

The meteorological data is tested for the first time in this study to estimate LAI and exhibits great importance in the models, though is not able to wholly explain grassland productivity or LAI as outlined by Neuwirth and Hofer (2013). The year 2023 had high temperatures and much precipitation in comparison to the three previous years. This and the low performance could mean that the models predict differently as they rely too strongly on this data as predictors. GPR is the only model that selected just the DOY as an auxiliary feature and not the meteorological data. It performed better in the test than the RF. CatBoost assigned the precipitation lower importance than RF too and outperformed the latter. This could imply that using meteorological data performs well within the same years though is not suitable for application on years with different temperatures and especially precipitation patterns.

The models that use the meteorological features are not able to properly identify the increase of LAI at the beginning of the growing season. This could be due to the greater importance of the DOY. It might also mean that the temperature does not facilitate identifying the start of the season as much as Wang et al. (2020) noted. Yet, it may contribute to predicting an increase in LAI thereafter until the first cut. In the later growing season, especially when management activities take place, the temperature would contradict the development of LAI, as no information on the vegetation situation over single meadows can be drawn from temperature measurements from meteorological stations.

Precipitation instead is related to the vegetation growth throughout the whole season. Li et al. (2019) found that precipitation is almost linearly related to LAI and highly determines the productivity (Gao et al., 2017), particularly in the early and mid-growing season (cf. Reinermann et al., 2020). In this study, however, the importance of precipitation in the LAI prediction models is lower. This could be because the region receives more precipitation in winter than in summer. Another reason might be the use of optical data, which is only available when the sky is clear. This way, days with precipitation, which means cloud coverage, were masked out and thus not included in the model training. For this, the model could not learn the relation between precipitation and LAI as not enough data was present. Also, the irrigation of the meadows, particularly in the dry Venosta Valley, could be a reason. It would falsify the precipitation values derived from the meteorological data of the weather stations. Drawing a relationship between the LAI on a said-to-be dry meadow with S1 data is then contradictory as the moisture content in the vegetation is indeed sensed by the S1.

As mentioned before, the spatial resolution of the meteorological data is 250 m in comparison to the 10 m of the Sentinel data. Even if the precipitation and temperature are considered homogenous for whole meadows, single pixels of a meadow that vary in LAI and S1 do have

the same DOY and meteorological values. Because they are more important than the S1 features, the meteorological data together with the other auxiliary features are probably the reason for the lower range in the predicted LAI between pixels in comparison to S2 LAI. Also as seen in the comparison with the management activities, the mowing events are not detected, and LAI is wrongly predicted. This means that the influence of the meteorological data could be misleading, and the machine learning algorithms are not able to learn that the influence of this data is to be considered differently with the progress in the growing season.

Alternatively, SMC data like from Greifeneder et al. (2021) could substitute the precipitation data and give actual information about the meadow derived from remote sensing instead of weather stations. Also, given the promising results in Castelli et al. (2023), SMC could be included as a feature in the future if available and preferably not masked by a land cover mask with lower resolution. Similarly, land surface temperature (LST) could be used to replace the temperature data used here. This would similarly represent on-site values and include the effects of the vegetation in altering the temperature by evapotranspiration which also depends on the LAI. However, LST from remote sensing like MODIS Terra has a spatial resolution of 1 km and would result in the same spatial smoothing effect as the meteorological station data.

4.3.3 DAY OF THE YEAR

The DOY is the most important feature for the RF, GPR, and CatBoost. The test for 2023 revealed that relying strongly on DOY might generalise too much over different meadows and pixels. An example of this is the prediction pattern in GPR: Values predicted for one day are similar and have a small range. This means that the model learns from the DOY to predict the LAI and thus generalises the values of one day.

The DOY is too important, and the models are less S1-driven. An example of that is that the mowing events are not properly identified but lower LAI is predicted by chance. It seems as if the models learned the seasonal pattern of LAI including the minima after the cuts from the DOY and do not derive lower LAI from S1 data. However, the meteorological data or the DOY do not directly represent the vegetation conditions on the grasslands. This means that the mowing practices are not derivable from the static features but must be drawn from the remote sensing data instead. The results imply that the models rely too strongly on the DOY and the other auxiliary predictors.

To avoid that in the future, the DOY should not be used anymore for modelling. It would force the models to rely more on the S1 features which represent the conditions on the meadows. However, the DOY is kept in the non-linear regression models as the best feature during the RFE, and models without it perform poorly. In GPR, the over-importance of the DOY could be reduced by using a MOGP. This way, the model learns the statistical relationship between the

S2 LAI- and S1 time series, and predictions are permanently based on remote sensing data (Pipia et al., 2019). The authors showed that this is especially advantageous over GPR for long-time gaps in S2 LAI. Particularly in times of only one active S1 sensor in orbit and a less dense time series resulting from that the MOGP could be preferred over the GPR. It allows also S1 to bear gaps and the spatial and temporal gaps in both time series can be filled simultaneously.

4.3.4 ALTITUDINAL CLASS

The altitudinal class is an important feature in CatBoost and RF. However, it generalises potential seasonal differences in assuming all meadows in one class have the same start of the phenological phase. As mentioned in 2.1.1, the start of the phases is 3.8 days later with every increase of 100 m in elevation in the Alps (Cornelius et al., 2013). This means that, e.g., meadows of the altitudinal class “Upper montane and subalpine” which lay between 1400 and 2500 m have potential differences in phenological phases of about 40 days in extreme cases. In relying too much on the class and the DOY, these meadows are treated similarly even if the differences would be multiple days.

A solution could be to include the phenological phase in the model training. In the study by Holtgrave et al. (2020), it was identified as the second most important feature for the estimation of S2 vegetation indices from S1 for different agricultural land uses. However, retrieving the phenological phase can be difficult and ideally, the management activities of the single parcels should be known to approximate the phenology (Holtgrave et al., 2020). Another possibility would be a less generalizing, finer classification into altitudinal belts to enable the model to learn more detailed phenological patterns for similar meadows and help interpret the S1 features. This could be done as given in the literature and not according to quantiles, avoiding classifying meadows into one class that are up to 1100 m in elevation apart. The classes would not have comparable sizes, and, for example, the subalpine class would be small. The risk of overfitting small classes should be assessed but can be avoided using cross-validation.

4.4 OUTLOOK

Based on the discussion above, the following should be considered in future work on this topic: Future field campaigns will not include sampling in lodged areas unless there is no other option. A buffer of 14.5 m to the meadow boundary will be respected to increase the number of validation samples, except for very small meadows. The farmers will be surveyed in more detail on management measures such as reseeding, and grass and herbaceous species will be assessed. The fmask will be carefully examined regarding the omitted masking of cloud shadow as this reduces the correlation of S2 to in-situ LAI.

Meadows on very steep slopes can be omitted. In S1 preprocessing, the ascending and descending orbits will be merged, potentially using a temporal smoother. The SAR signal will be decomposed into the different types of scattering by a polarimetric decomposition. If already available, the S1 NRB by ESA should be investigated as an alternative to the S1 RTC from the Microsoft Planetary Computer.

As alternative auxiliary predictors, SMC data could substitute the precipitation data from the meteorological stations if it has a suitable resolution and covers the grassland meadows. A less generalising classification into altitudinal classes can be assessed. If available, predictors regarding management activities or intensity could be used in the models. The DOY should be omitted to base the prediction more on the remote sensing data. Considering that especially GPR takes a multiple for training and working memory, AL will be examined to improve its performance. The MOGP could be beneficial for the gap-filling especially with a lower temporal resolution of S1 until the launch of S1 C. The hyperparameters of CatBoost can be further explored.

5 CONCLUSION

This thesis investigated the potential of Sentinel-1 (S1) Radiometrically Terrain Corrected (RTC) SAR data together with auxiliary predictors for the spatial gap-filling of Leaf Area Index (LAI) from Sentinel-2 (S2) optical data. Different machine learning regressors were trained and validated over Alpine grasslands in North-Eastern Italy for the years 2020-2022 and tested against in-situ measurements collected over eight forage production meadows and unseen test meadows in 2023. The Random Forest Regressor (RF) was the best-performing model on the validation set ($R^2=0.70$, $RMSE=0.97$). Models using the auxiliary predictors day of the year (DOY), altitudinal class, and meteorological data outperformed models trained on S1 features only. It shows that S1 is difficult to interpret even for non-linear regressors in the mountainous study area. However, the models performed little when transferred to unseen meadows and to the year 2023 which revealed that they are not robust. The CatBoost regressor was the best-suited modelling approach using S1 and all auxiliary features and achieved $R^2=0.16$ and $RMSE=1.34$. It surpassed the Gaussian Process Regressor (GPR, $R^2=0.11$, $RMSE=1.37$). The RF could not prove itself in the test, although it was advantageous for individual in-situ meadows, and the linear regressor (LR) failed. The validation against the in-situ LAI stated strong underestimations with high RMSE errors for all models. The low performance is accounted to the models relying too strongly on the auxiliary data as the management activities could not be properly identified. In conclusion, S1, especially using a CatBoost or GPR algorithm, has a large but improvable potential to accurately fill the cloud-related gaps in S2 LAI over Alpine grasslands. The S1 features VV, VH, their product, and the square difference are especially useful. Caution should be taken when using auxiliary predictors as these do not represent real conditions on the meadows and easily gain too much importance in the models which leads to a generalization of the gap-filled LAI. Large-scale, and long-term applications need to be improved to ensure the reliability and robustness of the models. Future studies should include the polarimetric decomposition of the SAR signal to enhance its interpretability without auxiliary features. In addition, a Multioutput Gaussian Process (MOGP) in combination with active learning (AL) is to be investigated.

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APPENDIX

Appendix A Specifications of the field sites based on the field measurements and Crespi et al. (2021), European Environment Agency (2016) and Rotter (1972).

Site	Size [ha]	Cuts [year ⁻¹]	Vegetation [%]			SMC [%]	Soil- type	Prec. [mm]	Temp. [°C]	Elev. [m]	Slope [°]
			G.	L.	O.						
R1	0.79	3,AG	52	19	29	39.05	BB	965	8.3	1284	1.7
R3	0.50	4	58	9	33	29.63	BB	965	5.4	1270	18.6
R4	1.05	3	71	15	14	39.45	BB	1003	5.2	1245	13.1
R5	1.00	3	56	16	28	37.19	BB	976	8.0	1285	3.7
F1	1.38	3	77	0	23	32.03	TF	908	8.1	956	2.7
F2	0.44	4	96	0	4	27.74	TF	905	8.7	969	4.2
L1	0.52	3,AG	45	33	22	21.61	BB	901	10.5	1353	6.5
L2	0.38	3,AG	54	32	14	23.87	SP	901	10.9	1334	17.0

Number of cuts per year and autumn grazing (AG); vegetation composition of graminoids (G), leguminoids (L) and other species (O); soil moisture content (SMC); soil types: Brown earth (BB), Terra fusca (TF), Semi-podsol (SP); annual total precipitation (Prec.) and annual mean temperature (Temp.) from 1981-2010.

Appendix B Validation of the S2 LAI against in-situ LAI for the different meadows.
Red: lodging is included, black: without lodging; in L1 and L2 no lodging occurred.

Meadow	r^2	MAE	RMSE	Bias	N	p-value
R1	0.38	1.85	2.29	-1.52	28	4.82e-04
	0.24	1.74	2.26	-1.33	23	1.78e-02
R3	0.54	1.08	1.39	-0.77	31	2.17e-06
	0.62	0.87	1.14	-0.45	23	7.87e-06
R4	0.65	1.78	2.39	-1.77	32	2.83e-08
	0.83	1.32	1.68	-1.31	21	1.16e-08
R5	0.59	1.62	2.06	-1.19	34	1.12e-07
	0.56	1.24	1.61	-0.72	28	4.33e-06
F1	0.89	2.24	2.4	-2.24	21	2.04e-10
	0.85	2.05	2.21	-2.05	16	4.68e-07
F2	0.50	1.56	1.72	-1.50	21	3.28e-04
	0.55	1.45	1.62	-1.38	17	7.04e-04
L1	0.78	1.36	1.70	-1.20	18	1.16e-06
L2	0.90	1.28	1.48	-1.19	21	3.85e-11
All	0.61	1.60	1.99	-1.40	206	1.07e-43
	0.62	1.47	1.82	-1.25	184	2.01e-40

Appendix C Model performance per feature set after feature selection and hyperparameter optimisation. Selected models are highlighted in bold.

Features	Model	R ²	RMSE	MAE	Bias	Time [hh:mm:ss]	Hyper- par.
All	LR	0.15	1.64	1.31	0.00	00:02:04	
	RF	0.70	0.97	0.68	0.02	00:53:32	
	GPR	0.07	1.69	1.37	0.06	01:34:10	
	CatBoost	0.54	1.20	0.90	0.00	00:37:20	10; 2000
S1	LR	0.06	1.72	1.39	0.00	00:01:18	
	RF	0.10	1.68	1.34	0.05	00:53:23	
	GPR	0.06	1.74	1.40	-0.05	01:18:23	
	CatBoost	0.08	1.70	1.38	0.00	00:39:59	5; 2000
S1, class	LR	0.07	1.71	1.39	0.00	00:01:14	
	RF	0.12	1.66	1.32	0.05	00:51:15	
	GPR	0.06	1.72	1.40	-0.02	01:53:33	
	CatBoost	0.10	1.68	1.36	0.00	00:39:15	9; 2000
S1, DOY	LR	0.06	1.72	1.39	0.00	00:01:29	
	RF	0.41	1.36	1.02	0.03	00:50:33	
	GPR	0.28	1.51	1.17	-0.03	01:29:15	
	CatBoost	0.39	1.38	1.06	0.00	00:42:19	10; 2000
S1, DOY, class	LR	0.07	1.71	1.39	0.00	00:01:31	
	RF	0.51	1.24	0.91	0.02	00:50:11	
	GPR	0.06	1.73	1.42	0.03	01:20:14	
	CatBoost	0.45	1.31	1.00	0.00	00:41:14	10; 2000
S1, DOY, meteo	LR	0.14	1.65	1.32	0.00	00:01:36	
	RF	0.66	1.04	0.74	0.02	00:53:26	
	GPR	0.06	1.74	1.41	-0.04	01:25:51	
	CatBoost	0.51	1.24	0.94	0.00	00:43:56	10; 2000
S1, meteo	LR	0.14	1.65	1.32	0.00	00:01:27	
	RF	0.43	1.34	1.01	0.04	00:52:30	
	GPR	0.07	1.70	1.37	-0.01	01:22:44	
	CatBoost	0.31	1.47	1.16	0.00	00:41:43	10; 2000
S1, meteo, class	LR	0.15	1.64	1.31	0.00	00:01:29	
	RF	0.53	1.22	0.90	0.03	00:50:58	
	GPR	0.13	1.67	1.34	-0.05	01:27:24	
	CatBoost	0.37	1.41	1.10	0.00	00:45:24	10; 2000

Appendix D Validation against S2 LAI according to altitudinal classes. Best performances are highlighted in bold.

Model	Class	R ²	RMSE	Bias	N
LR	All	-153.38	18.06	-2.36	289601
	S Subalpine + upper montane	-2.45	2.87	-2.51	33181
	S Lower montane	-432.52	31.21	-2.4	69269
	S Colline	-266.73	21.6	-2.12	48734
	S Submontane	-9.1	4.63	-2.06	50365
	N Lower montane	-4.77	3.6	-2.63	30710
	N Colline	-51.44	10.25	-2.86	19949
	N Submontane	-5.44	3.48	-2.35	25207
	N Subalpine + upper montane	-3.29	3.1	-2.6	12186
RF	All	-0.01	1.46	0.4	289601
	S Subalpine + upper montane	0.02	1.53	0.62	33181
	S Lower montane	-0.02	1.51	0.48	69269
	S Colline	-0.29	1.5	0.54	48734
	S Submontane	-0.13	1.55	0.55	50365
	N Lower montane	0.27	1.28	0.06	30710
	N Colline	0.15	1.31	-0.07	19949
	N Submontane	0.18	1.24	0.03	25207
	N Subalpine + upper montane	0.01	1.49	0.5	12186
GPR	All	0.11	1.37	0.22	289601
	S Subalpine + upper montane	0.32	1.27	0.35	33181
	S Lower montane	0.17	1.36	0.16	69269
	S Colline	-0.14	1.41	0.23	48734
	S Submontane	0	1.46	0.17	50365
	N Lower montane	0.26	1.29	0.26	30710
	N Colline	0.05	1.38	-0.02	19949
	N Submontane	0.04	1.34	0.21	25207
	N Subalpine + upper montane	0.02	1.48	0.54	12186
Cat-Boost	All	0.16	1.34	0.09	289601
	S Subalpine + upper montane	0.29	1.3	0.23	33181
	S Lower montane	0.13	1.4	0.26	69269
	S Colline	0.07	1.28	0.12	48734
	S Submontane	0.08	1.4	0.19	50365
	N Lower montane	0.26	1.29	-0.13	30710
	N Colline	0.13	1.32	-0.36	19949
	N Submontane	0.22	1.21	-0.21	25207
	N Subalpine + upper montane	0.13	1.4	0.13	12186

Appendix E Validation against in-situ and S2 LAI. Best performances are highlighted in bold.

Plot	Model	In-situ LAI				S2 LAI			
		R ²	RMSE	Bias	N	R ²	RMSE	Bias	N
All	LR	-1.05	3.6	-2.53	129	-0.05	1.44	0.09	1463
	RF	-0.95	3.51	-2.55	129	-0.23	1.56	-0.52	1463
	GPR	-0.78	3.35	-2.23	129	-0.06	1.45	-0.2	1463
	CatBoost	-0.86	3.43	-2.54	129	-0.26	1.58	-0.51	1463
F1	LR	-0.83	4.29	-2.81	24	0.22	1.16	0.61	276
	RF	-0.62	4.04	-2.82	24	0.61	0.82	-0.08	276
	GPR	-0.7	4.13	-2.58	24	0.58	0.85	0.04	276
	CatBoost	-0.49	3.87	-2.77	24	0.48	0.95	-0.29	276
F2	LR	-1.14	2.44	-1.67	10	-1.34	1.74	1.07	81
	RF	-1.25	2.5	-1.34	10	-1.77	1.89	0.17	81
	GPR	-0.76	2.21	-1.37	10	-1.49	1.8	0.3	81
	CatBoost	-1.3	2.53	-1.92	10	-2.24	2.05	0.07	81
L1	LR	-0.7	2.76	-1.74	16	0.24	1.31	0.05	52
	RF	-0.1	2.22	-1.36	16	0.51	1.05	-0.26	52
	GPR	-0.34	2.45	-1.27	16	0.55	1.01	-0.06	52
	CatBoost	-0.25	2.37	-1.49	16	0.35	1.22	-0.25	52
L2	LR	-1.52	4.52	-3.35	3	-0.32	1.44	0.49	24
	RF	-1.08	4.11	-3.2	3	-0.23	1.39	0.33	24
	GPR	-1.38	4.39	-3.14	3	-0.43	1.5	0.54	24
	CatBoost	-0.82	3.85	-3.03	3	-0.23	1.39	0.04	24
R1	LR	-2.84	3.96	-3.29	24	-0.86	1.48	0.46	210
	RF	-2.65	3.86	-3.46	24	-1.01	1.54	-0.36	210
	GPR	-2.22	3.62	-3.02	24	-1.3	1.64	0.23	210
	CatBoost	-2.44	3.75	-3.27	24	-0.84	1.47	-0.13	210
R3	LR	- Inf	1.61	-1.61	1	-0.56	1.31	0.51	16
	RF	- Inf	2.02	-2.02	1	-1.08	1.52	-0.1	16
	GPR	- Inf	1.9	-1.9	1	-1.04	1.5	0.04	16
	CatBoost	- Inf	2.21	-2.21	1	-0.86	1.43	-0.28	16
R4	LR	-0.92	3.45	-2.25	26	-0.35	1.47	-0.16	510
	RF	-0.77	3.31	-2.23	26	-0.6	1.6	-0.58	510
	GPR	-0.56	3.11	-1.87	26	-0.38	1.49	-0.31	510
	CatBoost	-0.61	3.15	-2.14	26	-0.47	1.54	-0.46	510
R5	LR	-1.18	3.47	-2.6	25	0.03	1.54	-0.57	294
	RF	-1.6	3.79	-2.92	25	-0.59	1.97	-1.29	294
	GPR	-0.93	3.27	-2.39	25	-0.07	1.61	-0.81	294
	CatBoost	-1.61	3.79	-2.88	25	-0.72	2.05	-1.31	294

Appendix F Validation against in-situ and S2 LAI according to altitudinal classes. Best performances are highlighted in bold.

Model	Class	In-situ LAI				S2 LAI			
		R ²	RMSE	Bias	N	R ²	RMSE	Bias	N
LR	S Subm.	-1.75	3.74	-2.94	53	-0.07	1.5	-0.09	544
	N. L. mont.	-0.81	3.2	-2.06	42	-0.28	1.46	-0.14	562
	S Colline	-0.83	3.84	-2.48	34	-0.05	1.32	0.72	357
	All	-1.05	3.6	-2.53	129	-0.05	1.44	0.09	1463
RF	S Subm.	-1.87	3.81	-3.16	53	-0.49	1.78	-0.82	544
	N. L. mont.	-0.53	2.94	-1.9	42	-0.46	1.56	-0.55	562
	S Colline	-0.66	3.66	-2.39	34	0.19	1.16	-0.02	357
	All	-0.95	3.51	-2.55	129	-0.23	1.56	-0.52	1463
GPR	S Subm.	-1.39	3.48	-2.71	53	-0.24	1.62	-0.32	544
	N. L. mont.	-0.46	2.88	-1.64	42	-0.27	1.45	-0.28	562
	S Colline	-0.67	3.67	-2.22	34	0.22	1.14	0.1	357
	All	-0.78	3.35	-2.23	129	-0.06	1.45	-0.2	1463
Cat-Boost	S Subm.	-1.77	3.75	-3.06	53	-0.54	1.8	-0.76	544
	N. L. mont.	-0.46	2.88	-1.89	42	-0.37	1.51	-0.44	562
	S Colline	-0.55	3.53	-2.52	34	0	1.28	-0.21	357
	All	-0.86	3.43	-2.54	129	-0.26	1.58	-0.51	1463

N. L. mont. = N Lower montane, S Subm. = S Submontane.

Appendix G Time series of the predicted LAI per model for the eight forage production meadows. Shown are the In-situ and S2 LAI, and the respective mowing events.

AFFIDAVIT

I hereby confirm that I have written the accompanying thesis by myself, without contributions from any sources other than those cited in the text and acknowledgements. This applies also to all graphics, drawings, maps, and images included in the thesis.

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